

JUDGING BY ALGORITHM? AI AND LEGITIMACY OF INTERNATIONAL ADJUDICATION

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ABSTRACT

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly generative AI, into judicial and dispute-resolution processes is increasingly viewed as inevitable. While much of the existing scholarship focuses on AI use in national legal systems, far less attention has been paid to its implications for international judicial institutions (IJIs), which already face longstanding structural challenges. Given their lack of centralized enforcement mechanisms and heavy dependence on state consent and public confidence, questions of legitimacy are especially acute in IJIs. This article examines how different ways of deploying AI in IJIs may affect both their normative and sociological legitimacy. The analysis emphasizes that “AI in courts” is not a uniform phenomenon: applications range from technical functions such as case management, translation, and evidence organization to more substantive decision-support tools, and, potentially, even automated decision drafting. The article, therefore, adopts a function-specific approach to legitimacy.

Regarding normative legitimacy, it evaluates AI through commonly cited criteria in international law scholarship, including state consent, procedural fairness, and democratic legitimacy. It argues that technical and administrative uses of AI may enhance legitimacy by improving access to justice and institutional efficiency, while more substantive uses raise concerns regarding consent, transparency, accountability, and the dynamic changes in international law. Turning to sociological legitimacy, the article reviews emerging empirical literature on public and professional perceptions of algorithmic decision-making in legal contexts and considers how these findings may apply to international adjudication. Existing studies suggest greater acceptance of AI in supportive and early-stage functions, particularly when human oversight is preserved, and lower acceptance in high-stakes adjudicative contexts. The article concludes that AI can both strengthen and undermine the legitimacy of IJIs, depending on how, where, and for what purposes it is deployed, and calls for function-specific governance frameworks and targeted empirical research on public perceptions in the international legal context.

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This article was funded by the European Union (ERC, 2021-COG, 101044195). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the authors only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Council. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the use of artificial intelligence (AI), particularly generative AI, has become an integral part of everyday life. The AI revolution has likewise reached both national and international judicial institutions (IJIs), as well as alternative dispute resolution bodies.¹ Although the introduction of AI into dispute resolution institutions is seen as inevitable, many questions remain regarding the appropriate ways to integrate AI into their various procedures such as translation, evidence gathering and decision-making. Until recently, most discussions about integrating AI into dispute resolution

¹ In this article, I refer to both international judicial and quasi-judicial institutions as “international judicial institutions.” See *infra* Part II for elaboration about the introduction of AI into national and international judicial institutions.

focused on national legal systems.² However, AI may be particularly consequential in the international judicial system, which has long faced structural challenges, including limited resources, inconsistent decisions, and alleged geopolitical biases.³ The use of AI has the potential to help address at least some of these problems.

These questions are already emerging in practice. In 2023, the Office of the Prosecutor of the International Criminal Court (the “ICC”) launched Project Harmony, an initiative that relies on AI tools to handle the growing scale and complexity of evidentiary materials.⁴ AI has also recently been introduced into international arbitration practices.⁵ While such developments suggest that AI may help address some of the structural challenges facing international judicial institutions, they also raise a range of new and unresolved concerns, most notably with respect to institutional legitimacy. While some of the relevant discourse is applicable to national judicial institutions, the stakes are even higher in the international judicial system, where legitimacy is especially critical given the absence of centralized enforcement power,⁶ limited democratic accountability,⁷ and a consent-based jurisdictional structure requiring states to “opt-in.” Although the legitimacy of IJIs is of particular importance, many such institutions are widely understood to face ongoing legitimacy challenges.⁸ Therefore, the introduction of AI poses both an opportunity and a risk when attempting to assess the possible implications of AI on the legitimacy of IJIs.

² See *infra* Part II.

³ See *infra* Section II.C.

⁴ ICC Prosecutor Karim A.A. Khan KC Announces Launch of Advanced Evidence Submission Platform, INT’L CRIM. CT. (May 24, 2023), <https://www.icc-cpi.int/news/icc-prosecutor-karim-aa-khan-kc-announces-launch-advanced-evidence-submission-platform-otplink>.

⁵ See e.g., Clearbrief: <https://clearbrief.com/>.

⁶ See Attila Tanzi, *Problems of Enforcement of Decisions of the International Court of Justice and the Law of the United Nations*, 6 EUR. J. INT’L L 539 (1995); W. Michael Reisman, *The Enforcement of International Judgments*, 63 AM. J. INT’L L. 1, 1–27 (1969); INTERNATIONAL COURT AUTHORITY (Karen J. Alter, Laurence R. Helfer & Mikael Rask Madsen eds., 2018) (explores the problem of non-compliance with and enforcement of judicial decisions of the ICJ).

⁷ See e.g., Jonathan W. Kuyper & Theresa Squatrito, *International Courts and Global Democratic Values: Participation, Accountability, and Justification*, 43 REV. INT’L STUD. 152, 152–76 (2017) (examines how international courts, despite concerns about the democratic deficit in world politics, can actually advance democratic values, such as equal participation, accountability, and public justification beyond the state); Andreas Von Staden, *The Democratic Legitimacy of Judicial Review Beyond the State: Normative Subsidiarity and Judicial Standards of Review*, 10 INT’L J. CONST. L., 1023–49 (2012) (examines how judicial review of national government acts by international courts raises questions about the democratic legitimacy of such review, linking it to the ideal of self-government); Madeline Morris, *The Democratic Dilemma of the International Criminal Court* 5 BUFF. CRIM. L. REV., 591–600 (2002) (examines the jurisdictional structure of the ICC in terms of the tension between legal accountability for international crimes and the democratic accountability of the ICC itself).

⁸ See e.g., Christian Reus-Smit, *International Crises of Legitimacy*, 44 INT’L POL., 157–74 (2007) (develops a theoretical foundation for understanding international crises of legitimacy, including defining what such a crisis entails for an actor or institution); Michael Zürn, *Global Governance and Legitimacy Problems*, 39 GOV’T & OPPOSITION, 260–87 (2004) (argues that the removal of decisions from the circuit of national and democratic responsibility creates normative problems that lead to growing acceptance issues and resistance to global governance); Jonas Tallberg, & Michael Zürn, *The Legitimacy and Legitimation of International Organizations: Introduction and Framework*, 14 REV. INT’L ORGS., 581–606 (2019) (examines how, when, and why international organizations gain, sustain, and lose legitimacy in world politics, directly addressing the core theme of legitimacy crises).

This article explores the various ways in which the introduction of AI into IJIs may affect their legitimacy. The two most important forms of legitimacy discussed in the literature are *normative legitimacy*, a more theoretical concept, and *sociological legitimacy*, which is largely an empirical issue.⁹ Normative legitimacy refers to an institution's "right to rule."¹⁰ Among its concerns are the standards by which political authority is considered rightful or justified, often grounded in democratic principles of accountability, participation, representation, and fairness.¹¹ Sociological legitimacy, by contrast, refers to the extent to which an institution is "widely believed to have the right to rule."¹² When assessing how deploying AI may affect the legitimacy of IJIs, it is misleading to speak of AI use in general terms, as AI applications range from more technical functions, such as case scheduling, to highly substantive ones, such as drafting judgments. Therefore, analyzing legitimacy and the rule of law in the context of judicial systems should also be attentive to the specific AI function that is used.

The article proceeds as follows. Part II reviews the introduction of AI into legal work in general and international legal work in particular. It also discusses how the introduction of AI can assist the work of IJIs. Part III examines how the use of AI can influence the normative legitimacy of the institutions, while Part IV focuses on the implications of AI use on sociological legitimacy. Part V concludes.

II. THE INTRODUCTION OF AI INTO JUDICIAL SYSTEMS

A. AI in Dispute Resolution Systems

With the introduction of large language models (LLMs) to the general public in recent years, AI has become an increasingly inseparable part of our lives, changing both private, social, and professional conduct.¹³ As AI technology develops, it gains increasingly more influence on different professions.¹⁴ For example, in healthcare and medicine, AI is used for medical imaging and diagnostics, clinical decision support, personalized medicine, and hospital operations.¹⁵ In transportation, AI is used for traffic management and

⁹ See generally Nienke Grossman, *The Normative Legitimacy of International Courts*, 86 TEMP. L. REV. 61 (2013) [hereinafter Grossman, *Normative Legitimacy*].

¹⁰ Allen Buchanan & Robert O. Keohane, *The Legitimacy of Global Governance Institutions*, 20 ETHICS & INT'L AFF. 405, 407 (2006); see also Laurence R. Helfer & Karen J. Alter, *Legitimacy and Lawmaking: A Tale of Three International Courts*, 14 THEORETICAL INQUIRIES L. 479 (2013).

¹¹ DAVID BEETHAM, *THE LEGITIMATION OF POWER* (1991); FRITZ W. SCHARPF, *GOVERNING IN EUROPE: EFFECTIVE AND DEMOCRATIC?* (1999).

¹² Buchanan & Keohane, *supra* note 10, at 407.

¹³ IBA report; Abby Cohen Smutny & Charles Nairac, *Arbitration and AI*, WHITE & CASE LLP (2025), https://www.whitecase.com/insight-our-thinking/2025-international-arbitration-survey-arbitration-and-ai?utm_source=chatgpt.com.

¹⁴ See generally, THOMSON REUTERS, *FUTURE OF PROFESSIONALS REPORT 2025: STRATEGIC AI ADOPTION: UNLOCKING INNOVATION AND MAXIMIZING RETURNS* (2025), <https://www.thomsonreuters.com/en/c/future-of-professionals>; Robert Bradshaw, *Deception and Detection: The Use of Technology in Assessing Witness Credibility*, 37 ARB. INT'L 707 (2021).

¹⁵ Simarjeet Kaur et al., *Medical Diagnostic Systems Using Artificial Intelligence (AI) Algorithms: Principles and Perspectives*, 8 IEEE ACCESS 228,049 (2020) (discussing using AI for medical diagnosis).

predictive maintenance,¹⁶ in engineering, for design optimization and quality control,¹⁷ and in finance, for fraud detection, credit scoring, and risk assessment.¹⁸ Finally, in public policy, AI is used for functions such as research design and evaluation, public service delivery, and regulatory enforcement.¹⁹

Similarly, the legal field has experienced increasing integration of legal technologies across different aspects of the work of legal professionals, including lawyers, paralegals, clerks, and judges. The relevant tools used by lawyers vary from general AI generative tools such as ChatGPT and Claud, to tools tailored especially for the needs of lawyers, such as Westlaw AI features,²⁰ Lexis+,²¹ Harvey AI,²² Lex Machina,²³ and Relativity.²⁴ Moreover, even specialized online tools for international law and arbitration, such as Jus Mundi (JusAI) and Clearbrief (a collaboration with the American Arbitration Association (AAA)), have introduced AI functions.²⁵ For example, in these tools, AI can be used for conducting legal research, transcription, drafting cross-examination questions, drafting documents, translation, discovery, and evaluating case value.²⁶ Some scholars argue that the introduction of legal AI tools can play a significant role in promoting access to justice for individuals who lack the resources to pay for a lawyer.²⁷

¹⁶ Selim Reza et al., *Urban Safety: An Image-Processing and Deep-Learning-Based Intelligent Traffic Management and Control System*, 21 SENSORS 7705 (2021) (discussing using AI in image processing and deep learning to address challenges in intelligent traffic management and control (ITMC) systems).

¹⁷ Muhammad Mohsin Kabeer, *Leveraging AI for Process Optimization: The Future of Quality Assurance in Lean Six Sigma*, 1 AM. J. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE & COMPUTING 87 (2025) (discussing using AI for process optimization).

¹⁸ Dimple Patil, *Artificial Intelligence in Financial Services: Advancements in Fraud Detection, Risk Management, and Algorithmic Trading Optimization* (Nov. 20, 2024) (arguing that financial institutions improve operational efficiency, client experiences, and risk mitigation using advances in machine learning, natural language processing, and predictive analytics).

¹⁹ THOMSON REUTERS, FUTURE OF PROFESSIONALS REPORT 2025: STRATEGIC AI ADOPTION: UNLOCKING INNOVATION AND MAXIMIZING RETURNS (2025), <https://www.thomsonreuters.com/en/c/future-of-professionals>; Robert Bradshaw, *Deception and Detection: The Use of Technology in Assessing Witness Credibility*, 37 ARB. INT'L 707 (2021); A. Arora et al., *Towards Intelligent Governance: The Role of AI in Policymaking and Decision Support for E-Governance*, in INFORMATION SYSTEMS FOR INTELLIGENT SYSTEMS 327 (Chakchai So In, Narendra D. Londhe, Nityesg Bhatt & Meels Kitsing eds., 2024) (discussing using AI in different forms of governance); Sorin-Alexandru Ionescu & Valentina Diaconita, *Transforming Financial Decision-Making: The Interplay of AI, Cloud Computing, and Advanced Data Management Technologies*, 18 INT'L J. COMPUTERS COMM'NS & CONTROL 5735 (2023) (discussing using AI in financial decision-making).

²⁰ Thomson Reuters, Westlaw AI, <https://legal.thomsonreuters.com/en/products/westlaw-precision>.

²¹ Lexis+, <https://www.lexisnexis.com/en-us/products/lexis-plus.page>.

²² Harvey AI, <https://www.harvey.ai/>.

²³ Lex Machina, <https://www.lexisnexis.com/community/insights/legal/lex-machina>.

²⁴ Relativity, <https://www.relativity.com/data-solutions/air/>.

²⁵ Jus Mundi, <https://jusmundi.com/en/>; Clearbrief, <https://clearbrief.com/>; see also Sanjana Reddy Jeeri & Vinita Singh, *Soft Law, Hard Justice: Regulating Artificial Intelligence in Arbitration*, 17 CONTEMP. ASIA ARB. J. 191 (2024).

²⁶ Stacie I. Strong, *Artificial Intelligence in Civil Justice Systems: An Empirical and Interdisciplinary Analysis and Proposal for Moving Forward*, 41 OHIO ST. J. ON DISP. RESOL. 8 (forthcoming 2026), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5239069>.

²⁷ Milan Markovic, *Rise of the Robot Lawyers*, 61 ARIZ. L. REV. 325, 340 (2019); Sangeet Sharma et al., *A Study of AI-Based Systems in the Judicial Interpretation of the Law*, in PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2ND INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON CYBER INTELLIGENCE AND INFORMATION RETRIEVAL 2023, 43 (Soumi Dutta et al. eds., 2024).

Globally, AI is gradually becoming integrated into different aspects of courts and judicial decision-making institutions. Among the most prominent examples is the use of the COMPAS system by Wisconsin courts to assess the likelihood of a defendant becoming a recidivist.²⁸ At the same time, critics have argued that the COMPAS system is racially biased.²⁹

A 2024 international arbitration report (which deliberately does not disclose the identity of the specific arbitration institutions), indicates that four out of eleven arbitration tribunals incorporated AI into different functions of their work.³⁰ According to the report, the functions fulfilled by AI were “preparation of casework reports, drafting of correspondence to the parties and arbitrators, tracking of case progress and compliance with procedural deadlines, assistance with hearing logistics/preparation, and scrutiny of draft awards and procedural orders.”³¹ One of the tribunals even acknowledged the use of AI to create auto-generated sections of arbitration awards.³² The AAA, for example, has invested considerable resources in AI innovations such as the Clearbrief tool, which allows arbitrators and parties to summarize and draft documents, including awards, and assign arbitrators.³³ Recently, the ICC, as a partial answer to critiques of ineffectiveness, launched the Project Harmony initiative employing AI tools to modernize evidence management, a task that is particularly complex in cases of mass atrocities.³⁴ Additionally, the Inter-American Court of Human Rights launched an AI-powered website that enables AI-assisted research of its decisions and case law.³⁵

²⁸ WISCONSIN DEP’T OF JUSTICE, CRIMINAL JUSTICE COORDINATING COUNCIL, COUNTY COMPAS ASSESSMENT & ADMINISTRATION: POLICY & PROCEDURE MANUAL (2013) <https://cjcc.doj.wi.gov/sites/default/files/subcommittee/Template%20COMPAS%20business%20process.pdf>.

²⁹ Julia Angwin et al., *Machine Bias: There’s Software Used Across the Country to Predict Future Criminals. And It’s Biased Against Blacks*, PROPUBLICA (2016) <https://www.propublica.org/article/machine-bias-risk-assessments-in-criminal-sentencing>; see also generally research into the COMPAS system: Nina Grgić-Hlača et al., *The Case for Process Fairness in Learning: Feature Selection for Fair Decision Making* (NeurIPS Symposium on Machine Learning and the Law 2016). The Case for Process Fairness in Learning: Feature Selection for Fair Decision Making, in Proc. NIPS Symposium on Machine Learning and the Law; Ryan P. Kennedy et al., *Trust in Public Policy Algorithms*, 84 J. POL., 1132–48 (2022); Niels van Berkel et al., *Crowdsourcing Perceptions of Fair Predictors for Machine Learning: A Recidivism Case Study*, 3 PROC. ACM HUM.–COMPUT. INTERACT. (CSCW) arts. 1–21.

³⁰ Maxim Osadchiy et al., *Are Arbitral Institutions Using Artificial Intelligence? The State of Play in Adopting AI*, KLUWER ARB. BLOG (2024), https://legalblogs.wolterskluwer.com/arbitration-blog/are-arbitral-institutions-using-artificial-intelligence-the-state-of-play-in-adopting-ai/?utm_source=chatgpt.com.

³¹ *Id.*

³² *Id.*

³³ *AI Tools and Technology*, AM. ARB. ASS’N, <https://www.adr.org/ai-tools-and-technology/>; AM. ARBITRATION ASS’N, AAA-ICDR® Launches New AAAi Panelist Search to Enhance Panelist Selection with AI Technology, PR NEWSWIRE (2024) <https://www.prnewswire.com/news-releases/aaa-icdr-launches-new-aaai-panelist-search-to-enhance-panelist-selection-with-ai-technology-302271705.html>; Strong, *supra* note 26, at 9.

³⁴ ICC Office of the Prosecutor, *ICC Prosecutor Karim A.A. Khan KC Announces Launch of Advanced Evidence Submission Platform: OTPLink*, INT’L CRIM. CT. (2023), https://www.icc-cpi.int/news/icc-prosecutor-karim-aa-khan-kc-announces-launch-advanced-evidence-submission-platform-otplink?utm_source=chatgpt.com.

³⁵ Themis IA, <https://themisia.corteidh.or.cr/>.

B. Concerns About the Introduction of AI into Dispute Resolution Institutions

Alongside widespread acknowledgment that some degree of AI integration into legal work is inevitable, there is a substantial body of theoretical scholarship examining the problems and risks associated with the introduction of AI tools into legal practice.³⁶ Commentators point out operational constraints, such as mistakes, hallucinations, and data-security risks.³⁷ There are also deeper concerns,³⁸ such as AI's capacity to exercise legal judgment, the "black box," opaque nature of AI reasoning that lacks explainability, biases inherent in the system, and lack of accountability.³⁹ With respect to AI's ability to exercise legal judgment, critics argue that AI is unable to grasp the details and nuances of documents, judgments, laws, and witness testimony,⁴⁰ and that it operates without empathy, emotions, or life experience.⁴¹ Moreover, theoretical concerns persist regarding the legitimacy of and trust in delegating certain parts of the judicial process to AI, especially in the judicial decision-making process itself.⁴²

As mentioned above, another concern relates to AI's black box problem, which refers to the difficulty, and, in some cases, even impossibility, of understanding how certain AI systems reach their decisions or outputs, even for their designers.⁴³ The inability to fully comprehend how the AI system reaches a certain legal decision is widely regarded as a major drawback, given that reasoning and transparency are integral to judicial practice and to the rule of law.⁴⁴

³⁶ See, e.g., Anna-Katharina Dhungel & Moreen Heine, *Cui Bono? Judicial Decision-Making in the Era of AI: A Qualitative Study on the Expectations of Judges in Germany*, 33(1) TATUP-ZEITSCHRIFT FÜR TECHNIKFOLGENABSCHÄTZUNG IN THEORIE UND PRAXIS 14, 14–20 (2024).

³⁷ Reddy and Singh, *supra* note 25; Strong, *supra* note 26; Ganesan, "Ethical Use of AI in Criminal Justice System," *Responsible Implementations of Generative AI for Multidisciplinary Use IGI Global* 337 (2025).

³⁸ Markovic, *supra* note 27, at 331–35; Benjamin Alarie et al., *How Artificial Intelligence Will Affect the Practice of Law*, 68 U. TORONTO L.J. 106, 122 (2017); Jakub Harasta et al., *It Cannot Be Right If It Was Written by AI: On Lawyers' Preferences of Documents Perceived as Authored by an LLM vs a Human*, A.I. & LAW (2024) 1, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10506-024-09422-w>; Branislav Urosevic, *Experts Agree: Artificial Intelligence Cannot Replace Lawyers*, LEGAL TIMES, Mar. 31, 2025, <https://www.lawtimesnews.com/resources/legal-technology/experts-agree-artificial-intelligence-cannot-replace-lawyers/391950>.

³⁹ Markovic, *supra* note 27, at 331–35; Veronika Fikfak & Laurence R. Helfer, *Automating International Human Rights Adjudication*, 46 MICH. J. INT'L L. 69, 25–33 (2024).

⁴⁰ Markovic, *supra* note 27.

⁴¹ Derick H. Lindquist & Ylli Dauta, *AI in International Arbitration: Need for the Human Touch*, J. DISP. RESOL. 39 (2021).

⁴² Margot E. Kaminski, *Binary Governance: Lessons from the GDPR's Approach to Algorithmic Accountability*, 92 SO. CAL. L. REV. 1529, 1542, 1549 (2019).

⁴³ Brandon Garrett & Cynthia Rudin, *The Right to a Glass Box: Rethinking the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Criminal Justice*, 109(3) CORNELL L. REV. 561–627 (2024), <https://ssrn.com/abstract=4275661>; Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39, at 37.

⁴⁴ Tatiana Dancy & Monika Zalnieriute *AI and Transparency in Judicial Decision Making*, OXFORD J. LEGAL STUD. (2025) (focuses on the acute risks for opacity posed by the growing use of predictive AI tools in judicial practice, especially those that generate probabilistic outputs from correlations identified in dataset); Ashley S. Deeks, *The Judicial Demand for Explainable Artificial Intelligence*, 119 COLUM. L. REV., 1829–50 (2019) (suggesting that demanding explanations from judges will play a seminal role in shaping the nature and form of "explainable AI"); Thomas Wischmeyer, *Artificial Intelligence and Transparency: Opening the Black Box*, in REGULATING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE 75, 75–101 (Thomas Wischmeyer & Timo Rademacher eds., 2019) (considering the inability of some AI systems to explain their causal determinants as less relevant than the current

Another major concern regarding AI use relates to accountability, particularly who bears responsibility for outputs and even potential errors. Whereas current laws and regulations impose legal and ethical responsibilities on legal professionals and institutions, critics argue that no one actor will be accountable for the actions of AI. It is therefore argued that clear and enforceable rules regarding accountability are essential.⁴⁵ With respect to possible biases, Fikfak and Helfer point to two primary sources of bias. The first is the biases embedded in the datasets on which algorithms train.⁴⁶ Because AI systems learn from existing data, they may reproduce and even effectively entrench these biases even further. The second form of bias emerges from interactions between humans and machines. In this type of bias, human decision-makers may defer to AI systems rather than using their own judgment.⁴⁷

As a result of such concerns, various bodies have issued national and international legislation, regulations, and guidelines on the use of AI in courts. For instance, the European Union AI Act classifies the use of AI in law enforcement and judiciary as “high-risk,” requiring human oversight, transparency, and accountability, stating that: “The use of AI tools can support the decision-making power of judges or judicial independence, but should not replace it: the final decision-making must remain a human-driven activity.”⁴⁸ Moreover, a UNESCO report warns that due to possible transparency problems, the use of AI in judicial systems may infringe the right to a fair trial.⁴⁹ Continuing, the report states that in the event that the judicial system uses AI: “sufficient safeguards are needed to guarantee inter alia the protection of fundamental human rights, the rule of law, judicial independence as well as the principle of human oversight, and to ensure a trustworthy, public interest-oriented and human-centric development and use of AI systems in the judiciary.”⁵⁰ Similar concerns were raised by the High Commissioner for Human Rights in his report on the right to privacy in the digital age,⁵¹ and by the U.N. Special Rapporteur on the Independence of Judges and Lawyers in her 2025 Report about AI in Judicial Systems.⁵²

lack of resources for courts and regulatory agencies to process information the systems already provide, framing “explainability” as an institutional challenge for the judiciary).

⁴⁵ Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39, at 33–36; Gabriel Lima et al., *Human Perceptions on Moral Responsibility of AI: A Case Study in AI-Assisted Bail Decision-Making*, in PROCEEDINGS OF THE 2021 CHI CONFERENCE ON HUMAN FACTORS IN COMPUTING SYSTEMS 1, 1–17 (2021); Caleb Furlough et al., *Attributing Blame to Robots: I. The Influence of Robot Autonomy*, 63 HUMAN FACTORS, 592–602 (2021).

⁴⁶ Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39, at 25.

⁴⁷ *Id.* at 29.

⁴⁸ AI Act, para. 61

⁴⁹ UNESCO, *Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence*, para. 37 (2021); *see also* UNESCO, *Guidelines for the Use of AI Systems in Courts and Tribunals* (2025).

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⁵¹ U.N. High Comm’r for Human Rights, *The Right to Privacy in the Digital Age*, U.N. Doc. A/HRC/48/31 (2021).

⁵² U.N. Special Rapporteur on the Independence of Judges and Lawyers, *Artificial Intelligence in Judicial Systems: Promises and Pitfalls*, U.N. Doc. A/80/169 (July 16, 2025); *see also* European Commission for the Efficiency of Justice, *Report on The Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Judiciary Based on the Information Contained in the Resource Centre on Cyberjustice and AI* (Feb. 28, 2025).

A more recent UNESCO report focusing specifically on the use of AI by courts and tribunals, introduces guidelines regarding integration of AI into judicial systems using key principles such as protection of human rights, proportionality, feasibility of benefits, safety, information security, accuracy and reliability, explainability, auditability, transparent and open justice, awareness and informed use, responsibility, accountability and contestability, human oversight and decision-making, human-centric and participatory design, multi-stakeholder governance, and collaboration.⁵³ Additionally, some of the leading international arbitration bodies have issued guidelines about the usage of AI in international arbitration and reports on the subject.⁵⁴ Across all frameworks, AI is confined to supporting technical functions, such as disclosure, whereas substantive decision-making and accountability must remain with humans. No guideline allows the transfer of core adjudicative authority to AI systems.

C. The Problems of International Courts and How AI Can Help to Solve Them

International judicial adjudication has faced numerous challenges in recent years. Although AI applications cannot resolve all these difficulties, they may help address at least some of them. This issue, while likely meriting a separate article of its own, is discussed briefly in this part.

International adjudication is frequently criticized for its inefficiency,⁵⁵ which can often arise with legally complex cases involving multiple documents, languages, states, and international treaties.⁵⁶ In addition, the pool of professionals qualified to adjudicate such cases is relatively small, thus leading to significant delays in the docket.⁵⁷ Moreover, the time taken to draft decisions and judgments themselves is regarded as excessive, and time limits are not sufficiently managed or enforced.⁵⁸ However, it seems that the most acute problem in international adjudication is insufficient resources. IJI's under-funding and resulting insufficient number of decision-makers and

⁵³ UNESCO, *Guidelines for the Use of AI Systems in Courts and Tribunals* 17 (Dec. 2025), https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000396582?fbclid=IwY2xjawPIImQtleHRuA2FlbQIxMABicmlkETFzRW1jQ1h2VON5TINsR2loc3JOYwZhcHBfaWQQMjIyMDM5MTc4ODIwMDg5MgABHhuNduoHmmyW1h3Zis4Vyd-FdGn7FL1tato_pQcWuurgjow7HgveBEWSama-_aem_BToWW19Hhn2if2h7m5JtQg.

⁵⁴ Stockholm Chamber of Commerce, *Guide to the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Cases Administered Under the SCC Rules* (2024), https://sccarbitrationinstitute.se/wp-content/uploads/2024/12/scc_guide_to_the_use_of_artificial_intelligence_in_cases_administered_under_the_scc_rules-1.pdf; SILICON VALLEY ARB. & MEDIATION CTR., *Guidelines on the Use of Artificial Intelligence in Arbitration* (2024), <https://svamc.org/wp-content/uploads/SVAMC-AI-Guidelines-First-Edition.pdf>; INT'L COUNCIL FOR COM. ARB., *Guideline on the Use of AI in Arbitration* (2025), https://www.ciarb.org/media/m5dl3pha/ciarb-guideline-on-the-use-of-ai-in-arbitration-2025-_final_march-2025.pdf.

⁵⁵ Paul Bennett Marrow et al., *Artificial Intelligence and Arbitration: The Computer as an Arbitrator—Are We There Yet?*, 74 DISP. RESOL. J. 35 (2020); Derick H. Lindquist & Ylli Dauta, *AI in International Arbitration: Need for the Human Touch*, 2021 J. DISP. RESOL., 39–64 (2021); Jaffar Alkhayer et al., *The Transformative Role of Artificial Intelligence in the Legal Profession and International Arbitration*, in CYBER INTELLIGENCE AND INFORMATION RETRIEVAL 1025 (S. Dutta et al. eds., 2024).

⁵⁶ Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39, at 78–87.

⁵⁷ Susan Franck et al., *The Diversity Challenge: Exploring the Invisible College of International Arbitration*, 53 COLUM. J. TRANSNAT'L L. 429 (2014); S.F. Ali, *Diversity in International Arbitration*, 20 DISP. RESOL. MAG. 13 (2013).

⁵⁸ Marrow et al., *supra* note 55.

support staff undermine their ability to efficiently perform the needed functions.⁵⁹

Another closely related challenge in IIJs is access to justice in those institutions,⁶⁰ which has become increasingly difficult due to the multinational, complex, and often lengthy nature of the proceedings. This problem is evident not only in proceedings before tribunals where individuals bring claims against states, such as the regional human rights courts and the quasi-judicial U.N. treaty bodies,⁶¹ but also in proceedings involving commercial companies that have opted for international arbitration clauses, including international investment arbitration.⁶² This difficulty is attributable to the fact that the costs of international arbitration have risen significantly in recent years, which may pose problems even for large corporations.⁶³

Finally, the international legal system has long been subject to criticism for alleged biases. For example, it has been argued that judges tend to rule in favor of their own states, of states that are geopolitically similar to their states of origin, and of particular blocs of states.⁶⁴ It is argued that these biases seriously undermine the legitimacy of international proceedings, a concern which is of special importance given the persistent problems surrounding the implementation of decisions of international courts.⁶⁵ Moreover, allegations of bias have also been raised in the context of investor–state arbitration, where arbitrators are said to be biased in favor of the investors, who usually come from developed states and against the states, which are usually developing

⁵⁹ Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39; Thomas S. Warrick & M. Cherif Bassiouni, *Organization of the International Criminal Court: Administrative and Financial Issues*, 25 DENV. J. INT'L L. & POL'Y 333 (1997); Michael O'Flaherty & Claire O'Brien, *Reform of UN Human Rights Treaty Monitoring Bodies: A Critique of the Concept Paper on the High Commissioner's Proposal for a Unified Standing Treaty Body*, 7 HUM. RTS. L. REV., 141–72 (2007) (discussing the context of U.N. treaty bodies).

⁶⁰ Vera Shikhelman, *Access to Justice in the United Nations Human Rights Committee*, 39 MICH. J. INT'L L. 453 (2018); Christopher A. Whytock, *Transnational Access to Justice*, 38 BERKELEY J. INT'L L. 154 (2020).

⁶¹ Shikhelman *supra* note 59.

⁶² Matthew Hodgson et al., *2021 Empirical Study: Costs, Damages and Duration in Investor–State Arbitration* (BIICL & Allen & Overy, June 2021), https://www.biicl.org/documents/136_isds-costs-damages-duration_june_2021.pdf.

⁶³ *Id.* For instance, in some cases, the costs of investor–state arbitration have exceeded US\$30m., a substantial amount for most parties, *see* Diane Desierto, *Rising Legal Costs Claimed by States in Investor–State Arbitrations: The Test of “Reasonableness” in Philip Morris v. Australia*, EJIL TALK! (July 12, 2017), [https://www.ejiltalk.org/rising-legal-costs-claimed-by-states-in-investor-state-arbitrations-the-case-of-philip-morris-v-australia/#:~:text=\(ii\)%20rules%20for%20allocating%20these,the%20services%20of%20international%20counsel](https://www.ejiltalk.org/rising-legal-costs-claimed-by-states-in-investor-state-arbitrations-the-case-of-philip-morris-v-australia/#:~:text=(ii)%20rules%20for%20allocating%20these,the%20services%20of%20international%20counsel).

⁶⁴ Eric A. Posner & Miguel F.P. de Figueiredo, *Is the International Court of Justice Biased?*, 34 J. LEGAL STUD. 599 (2005) (empirically exploring biases in the ICJ); Erik Voeten, *The Impartiality of International Judges: Evidence from the European Court of Human Rights*, 102 AM. POL. SCI. REV. 417 (2008) (empirically exploring voting patterns in the ECtHR); Vera Shikhelman, *Geography, Politics and Culture in the United Nations Human Rights Committee*, 28 EUR. J. INT'L L. 845 (2017) (empirically exploring geopolitical and cultural biases in the U.N.H.R.C.).

⁶⁵ Nienke Grossman, *Legitimacy and International Adjudicative Bodies*, 41 GEO. WASH. INT'L L. REV., 107 (2009).

states.⁶⁶ It has also been argued that the awards and remedies international courts award to parties suffer from inconsistency.⁶⁷

Given that some of these problems arise from insufficient resources, AI may prove to be of value for international courts. In their article “Automating International Human Rights Adjudication,” Fikfak and Helfer describe in detail the different possible applications of automation, including AI, for international human rights adjudication, as well as the possible problems that might arise from deploying AI.⁶⁸ AI can help both the institutions themselves and the litigators and their lawyers. As mentioned above, at a relatively low cost, legal AI tools can help simplify difficult processes such as managing vast amounts of evidence, complex discovery procedures, translation, managing witnesses’ hearings, protocols, and scheduling of proceedings.⁶⁹ Moreover, by using these and the many other available tools, lawyers reduce the cost of the proceedings for adjudicants and thereby increase the accessibility of international institutions. Finally, using decision-support systems may arguably reduce the criticism regarding biases and inconsistencies in the decisions of international institutions.⁷⁰

III. AI AND THE LEGITIMACY OF INTERNATIONAL COURTS

The international system in which IJIs operate is extremely complex, and therefore every change and innovation in those institutions should be carefully considered from multiple perspectives. This is particularly true regarding introducing AI into the legal work of IJIs. As noted above, the use of AI in legal practice raises a range of practical and theoretical concerns, which may be further amplified in the international context. This article seeks to explore how the introduction of AI into IJIs may affect their legitimacy. The intention is not to provide a binary answer as to whether the use of AI increases or decreases the legitimacy of IJIs, but rather to provide analytic tools for assessing how AI use can affect legitimacy. The article examines normative and sociological legitimacy, which are discussed in detail in the following.

A. Normative Legitimacy

Normative legitimacy, as defined by Buchanan and Keohane, refers to the claim that “an institution has a right to rule.”⁷¹ This issue is particularly relevant in relation to IJIs, which are considered among the most influential institutions in the international political sphere.⁷² Indeed, according to Article

⁶⁶ Sergio Puig & Anton Strezhnev, *Affiliation Bias in Arbitration: An Experimental Approach*, 46 J. LEGAL STUD., 371–98 (2017).

⁶⁷ Juan Carlos Ochoa-Sánchez, *Review by the Inter-American Court of Human Rights and Domestic Reparation Programmes: Towards a More Nuanced Approach*, 25 INT’L J. HUM. RTS., 895–924 (2021).

⁶⁸ *Id.* at 7–14.

⁶⁹ *Id.*

⁷⁰ See discussion, *infra* Part III.

⁷¹ Buchanan & Keohane, *supra* note 10, at 407. See also Laurence R. Helfer & Karen J. Alter, *Legitimacy and Lawmaking: A Tale of Three International Courts*, 14 THEORETICAL INQUIRIES L. 479 (2013).

⁷² See generally, José E. Alvarez, THE IMPACT OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS ON INTERNATIONAL LAW (2016). See, e.g., Jeffrey K. Staton & Will H. Moore, *Judicial Power in Domestic and International Politics*, 65 INT’L ORG., 553–87 (2011) (discussing the scope of international judicial bodies, including the ICJ, the ECtHR, and the WTO, that are permanent tribunals using international law to issue legally binding decisions); Karen J.

38(1)(d) of the Statute of the International Court of Justice (ICJ),⁷³ international courts not only settle the specific dispute before them, but they also create binding norms of international law.⁷⁴ Therefore, given that international institutions, and courts in particular, exercise significant power over people worldwide, their normative legitimacy is of special importance.⁷⁵

Within the broader discussion about normative legitimacy, Joseph Raz's theory of normative legitimacy of institutions should also be noted.⁷⁶ Raz's "service conception" theory posits that the legitimate authority of an institution depends on its ability to serve those subject to its jurisdiction and power.⁷⁷ Therefore, an institution's authority is justified only if it helps people to better comply with the reasons that already apply to them.⁷⁸ This means that an institution is legitimate if, by following its directives, people are more likely to act in accordance with relevant obligations and considerations than if they were to decide independently.⁷⁹ Applying Raz's theory to international institutions, an IJI is legitimate if it helps states (and other relevant entities) better conform to international law and justice. Clearly, Raz's account, focusing on outcomes, such as helping people act properly, rather than processes, such as democratic participation, is instrumental rather than procedural.⁸⁰ Therefore, to evaluate the normative legitimacy of an international institution according to Raz's theory, we need to better understand how the use of AI by IJIs has the potential to increase (or decrease) states' compliance with their already existing international law obligations.

Alongside, and sometimes in addition to Raz's theory, a substantial body of scholarship addresses the criteria by which the IJIs should be assessed to evaluate their normative legitimacy. The two "classical" criteria for

Alter et al., *How Context Shapes the Authority of International Courts*, 79 LAW & CONTEMP. PROBS. 1, 1–46 (2016) (analyzing how institutional, political, and social contexts influence the authority and influence of international judicial institutions); Armin von Bogdandy & Ingo Venzke, *International Judicial Institutions in International Relations: Functions, Authority and Legitimacy*, in ROUTLEDGE HANDBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATION, 461–72 (Thomas G. Weiss & Rorden Wilkinson eds., 2013) (noting that international courts and tribunals now perform a number of different functions within the context of global governance, exercising authority by way of lawmaking beyond the confines of concrete cases).

⁷³ Statute of the International Court of Justice, June 26, 1945, 59 Stat. 1055, 33 U.N.C.I.O. 993.

⁷⁴ For a general discussion on the role of judicial precedents in international courts, see Yuval Shany, *No Longer a Weak Department of Power? Reflections on the Emergence of a New International Judiciary*, 20 EUR. J. INT'L L. 73, 75 (2009); MOHAMED SHAHABUDEEN, PRECEDENT IN THE WORLD COURT 91 (2007); Bogdandy & Venzke, *supra* note 72, at 19 (discussing precedent in international law in light of the legitimacy of legal institutions); Tom Ginsburg, *Bounded Discretion in International Judicial Lawmaking*, 43 VA. J. INT'L L. 631, 639 (2005) (discussing the importance and inevitability of judicial lawmaking in international law, as well as its boundaries).

⁷⁵ Grossman, *Normative Legitimacy*, *supra* note 9, at 104.

⁷⁶ Joseph Raz, *The Morality of Freedom* 63 (1986); see also John Tasioulas, *Parochialism and the Legitimacy of International Law*, in PAROCHIALISM, COSMOPOLITANISM, AND THE FOUNDATIONS OF INTERNATIONAL LAW 16, 19 (M.N.S. Sellers ed., 2012); Lukas H. Meyer & Pranay Sanklecha, INTRODUCTION, TO LEGITIMACY, JUSTICE AND PUBLIC INTERNATIONAL LAW 5–8 (Lukas H. Meyer, ed., 2009).

⁷⁷ See also Grossman, *supra* note 9, at 100.

⁷⁸ *Id.*

⁷⁹ See Grossman, *supra* note 9, at 97–101.

⁸⁰ Gürkan Çapar, *The Service Conception, Specification Problem and Its Moral Foundations*, RES PUBLICA, 1–28 (2025); Ammar Naqvi, *A Theory of Obligation at Law*, JUS COGENS, 1 (2025).

normative legitimacy are *state consent* and *procedural fairness* for litigants.⁸¹ Although newer scholarship has at times criticized these two components as somewhat outdated with regard to the legitimacy of international institutions,⁸² they may remain relevant for evaluating normative legitimacy and the use of AI. However, as Grossman discusses in her article on the normative legitimacy of international courts,⁸³ the rising power of IJIs and their wide-ranging impact on people throughout the world call for the consideration of additional criteria.⁸⁴

It should be noted that there is no agreed-upon list of criteria on the normative legitimacy of IJIs found in the literature. Some scholars even argue that no uniform set of criteria should apply across all institutions; instead, the specific functions each institution was designed to accomplish should be taken into account.⁸⁵ To analyze the implications of using AI in IJIs on their normative legitimacy, I focus on the most common criteria discussed in the literature: state consent, procedural fairness for the litigants, consistency with the object and purpose of the normative regimes that the international institution interprets and applies, democratic legitimacy, effectiveness and implementation, and adherence to the law.⁸⁶

i. State Consent

State consent is regarded as one of the most critical components of international law in general, and of normative legitimacy in particular.⁸⁷ This position stems primarily from the state consent's foundational role in the two main sources of international law – treaties and customary international law.⁸⁸

⁸¹ Grossman, *supra* note 9, at 65–68; Rüdiger Wolfrum, *Legitimacy of International Law from a Legal Perspective: Some Introductory Considerations*, in LEGITIMACY OF INTERNATIONAL LAW 1, 6 (Rüdiger Wolfrum & Volker Röben eds., 2008); Martti Koskeniemi, *The Ideology of International Adjudication and the 1907 Hague Conference*, in TOPICALITY OF THE 1907 HAGUE CONFERENCE, THE SECOND PEACE CONFERENCE, 127 (Yves Daudet ed., 2008); *see also* Armin von Bogdandy & Ingo Venzke, *Beyond Dispute: International Judicial Institutions as Lawmakers*, 12 GERMAN L.J. 979, 980 (2011).

⁸² *See* Grossman, *supra* note 9; Allberg & Zürn *supra* note 8; Eva Erman, *A Function-Sensitive Approach to the Legitimacy of Global Governance*, 50 BRITISH J. POL. SCI. 1001 (2018).

⁸³ Grossman, *supra* note 9.

⁸⁴ *Id.* at 79–102.

⁸⁵ Erman, *supra* note 9, at 1001–24.

⁸⁶ *See* Grossman, *supra* note 9; Antoinette Scherz & Oisín Suttle, *Legitimate International Authority and Institutional Diversity*, CRITICAL REVIEW OF INTERNATIONAL SOCIAL AND POLITICAL PHILOSOPHY (2025); Silje A. Langvatn, *What Is It We Disagree About When We Disagree About the Legitimacy of an Institution? A Framework for Analyzing Legitimacy's Institutional-Context Sensitivity*, 38 ETHICS & INT'L AFFS. (2025); Cecily Rose, *Justifying Arguments About Selection Procedures for Judges at International Courts and Tribunals: A Response to Nienke Grossman*, AJIL UNBOUND 110 (2016) 86–91; Neus Torbisco-Casals, *The Legitimacy of International Courts: The Challenge of Diversity*, 52 J. POL. PHIL. 491–515 (2021); Andreas Follesdal, *Survey Article: The Legitimacy of International Courts*, 8 J. POL. PHIL. (2020); Geir Ulfstein, *The Human Rights Treaty Bodies and Legitimacy Challenges*, LEGITIMACY AND INTERNATIONAL COURTS 284–304 (Nienke Grossman, Harlan Grant Cohen, Andreas Follesdal & Geir Ulfstein eds., 2018).

⁸⁷ Wolfrum, *supra* note 81.

⁸⁸ *See, e.g.*, JAMES A. GREEN, THE PERSISTENT OBJECTOR RULE IN INTERNATIONAL LAW (2016) (explaining the persistent objector rule as a mechanism that preserves the positivist notion that international law only binds a state if it has consented to be bound by it); I.M. Lobo de Souza, *The Role of State Consent in the Customary Process*, 44 INT'L & COMPAR. L.Q. 521 (1995) (examining whether the expression of State consent is a necessary step in the procedure that leads to the formation of a customary rule); Joel P. Trachtman, *Persistent Objectors, Cooperation, and the Utility of Customary International Law*, 21 DUKE J. COMPAR. & INT'L L. 221 (2010) (examining the persistent objector rule in customary international law, which directly addresses how a state's

While the consent component is at times criticized for being somewhat outdated, failures to satisfy this requirement have been central to major critiques of the legitimacy of international courts.⁸⁹

The issue of breach of consent was raised in a few contexts where it was claimed that a lack of consent affected the legitimacy of the IJIs. The first context involves cases in which it was claimed that states never gave their consent to the jurisdiction in the first place, such as the case of *Nicaragua v. the United States (Case Concerning Military and Paramilitary Activities in and Against Nicaragua)* in the ICJ.⁹⁰ In this case, the United States claimed that the ICJ lacked jurisdiction over the case, given the U.S. reservation to jurisdiction under Article 36(2) of the ICJ Statute.⁹¹ Another example concerns challenges to the jurisdiction of the ICC in cases brought against Israeli officials, where Israel has argued that the court lacks jurisdiction for various reasons, including the fact that Israel is not a party to the ICC.⁹²

This last example leads to an additional critique regarding breaches of consent that focuses on international courts allegedly interpreting provisions of international treaties either too widely or too narrowly.⁹³ This concern is often raised in relation to the characterization of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR) as a “living instrument,” which allows the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) to interpret the ECHR in light of

lack of consent during the rule’s formation affects its application); Duncan B. Hollis, *Why State Consent Still Matters—Non-State Actors, Treaties, and the Changing Sources of International Law*, 23 BERKELEY J. INT’L L. 137 (2005) (arguing that although non-state actors are increasingly involved in applying and implementing treaties, the treaty paradigm generally remains preconditioned on state consent).

⁸⁹ MALCOLM SHAW, *INTERNATIONAL LAW* 58–110 (9th ed. 2021); JAMES CRAWFORD, *BROWNLIE’S PRINCIPLES OF PUBLIC INTERNATIONAL LAW* 18–44 (9th ed. 2019).

⁹⁰ *Military and Paramilitary Activities in and Against Nicaragua (Nicar. v. U.S.)*, Jurisdiction and Admissibility, 1984 I.C.J. 392 (Nov. 26).

⁹¹ The U.S. accepted the ICJ’s compulsory jurisdiction under art. 36(2) of the Statute, but with a major reservation—that the ICJ had no jurisdiction over disputes arising under multilateral treaties, unless all affected parties were before the Court. The U.S. argued that Nicaragua’s claims, including violations of the U.N. Charter and the OAS Charter, fell under multilateral treaties, so the ICJ lacked jurisdiction. The ICJ rejected this claim as it argued that the claims rely also on customary international law.

⁹² Leila Nadya Sadat, *The Conferred Jurisdiction of the International Criminal Court*, NOTRE DAME L. REV. 99 (2023): 549; Margot Devlaminck, *The Israeli–Palestinian Question Before the International Criminal Court: Does the Court Have Jurisdiction?* (2023, Ghent University); Daniel Benoliel & Ronen Perry, *Israel, Palestine, and the ICC*, 32 MICH. J. INT’L L. 73 (2010).

⁹³ See, e.g., Fuad Zarbiyev, *Judicial Activism in International Law—A Conceptual Framework for Analysis*, 3(2) J. INT’L DISP. SETTLEMENT 247–78 (2012) (noting that that judicial activism is relevant to the interpretation of law, and judicial discretion increases with indeterminacy in the law’s interpretation); Gerald G. Fitzmaurice, *Law and Procedure of the International Court of Justice: Treaty Interpretation and Certain Other Treaty Points*, 28 BRIT. Y.B. INT’L L. 1 (1951) (arguing that the “teleological” method can involve tribunals in legislative instead of judicial or interpretative functions, particularly if it goes beyond interpretation to alter the apparent sense of a phrase or supplement texts); Joost Pauwelyn & Manfred Elsig, *The Politics of Treaty Interpretation: Variations and Explanations Across International Tribunals*, in *INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVES ON INTERNATIONAL LAW AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS: THE STATE OF THE ART* 445–74 (Jeffrey L. Dunoff & Mark A. Pollack eds., 2013) (discussing different approaches of treaty interpretation by international courts); Pieter Kooijmans, *The ICJ in the 21st Century: Judicial Restraint, Judicial Activism, or Proactive Judicial Policy*, 56(4) INT’L & COMPAR. L.Q. 741–53 (2007) (contrasting the ICJ’s approach with that of the ECJ and the ECtHR, whose jurisdictions flow automatically from their basic treaties, allowing them to render influential, ground-breaking decisions that might be perceived as wider interpretations.)

contemporary values.⁹⁴ Another example for alleged over-interpretation are claims concerning the lack of state consent arose when the U.N. Human Rights Committee stated in its General Comment 33 that the views it issues in individual communications under the First Optional Protocol are *de facto* legally binding on states.⁹⁵ In response, some states argued that these positions departed from the original intention behind the individual communications procedure and amounted to an over-interpretation of the Committee's authority.⁹⁶

Given the continuing relevance of consent in international law, it is important to examine what the treaties establishing IJIs may indicate about the possibility of using AI both in the more technical and the more substantial parts of their work. Since AI was not even envisioned when the treaties establishing IJIs were drafted, there is a question of how AI can be integrated in accordance with the original consent of the state parties. Here, as in other areas, the distinction between the more technical functions and the more substantive decision-making support functions can be of special importance.

Almost every treaty establishing an IJI contains an article about the composition of the judicial bench. This includes the number of judges, as well as diversity criteria, such as geography, legal systems, professional background, and, in the newer treaties, gender.⁹⁷ Moreover, many treaties also specify the qualifications, competence, and moral character of the judges;⁹⁸ for example, Article 2 of the ICJ reads as follows:

“The Court shall be composed of a body of independent judges, elected regardless of their nationality from among persons of high moral character, who possess the qualifications required in their respective countries for appointment to the

⁹⁴ See https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2021836;https://www.cambridge.org/core/books/abs/constituting-europe/echr-as-a-living-instrument-its-meaning-and-legitimacy/ED7EA3F99CC8DB88BF2691FF9B44C25B.

⁹⁵ ICCPR, General Comment 33—The Obligations of States Parties Under the Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, CCPR/C/GC/33 (Nov. 5, 2008); see also SUZANNE EGAN, THE UN HUMAN RIGHTS TREATY SYSTEM: LAW AND PROCEDURE, 262–63 (2019).

⁹⁶ OFFICE OF HIGH COMMISSIONER FOR HUMAN RIGHTS, GENERAL CALL FOR WRITTEN COMMENTS SUBMISSIONS RECEIVED FROM STATE PARTIES (2008), <http://www.ohchr.org/EN/HRBodies/CCPR/Pages/GC33-ObligationsofStatesParties.aspx>.

⁹⁷ Currently, almost all of the statutes establishing international judicial institutions have provisions regarding the diversity of the decision-makers. For instance, art. 9 of the Statute of the ICJ States that: “At every election, the electors shall bear in mind not only that the persons to be elected should individually possess the qualifications required, but also that in the body as a whole the representation of the main forms of civilization and of the principal legal systems of the world should be assured.” Over time, awareness of the significance of diversity in judicial institutions has grown, and, therefore, one of the new major international courts, the ICC, has an exceptionally detailed provision regarding diversity of the judiciary. Article 36 of the Statute of the ICC (the Rome Statute) indicates that there should be diversity in professional background, representation of the principal legal systems, equitable geographical representation, and gender balance. RUTH MACKENZIE ET AL., SELECTING INTERNATIONAL JUDGES: PRINCIPLE, PROCESS AND POLITICS 24 (2010); Ruth Mackenzie, *The Selection of International Judges*, in INTERNATIONAL ADJUDICATION 737, 743–47 (Cesare P.R. Romano, Karen J. Alter & Yuval Shany eds., 2014).

⁹⁸ *Id.*

highest judicial offices, or are jurisconsults of recognized competence in international law.”⁹⁹

The fact that the statutes establishing IJIs have such detailed provisions regarding the composition of the judiciary indicates that states attach great weight to the identity, qualifications, and background of the members of the elected bench. Therefore, introducing AI into decision-making in place of human judges in IJIs without the prior consent of participating states may be seen as a significant breach of consent and, consequently, as undermining the normative legitimacy of the court. However, as mentioned earlier, AI encompasses a wide range of tools that may be applied to the work of courts, and certain forms of decision-making support for human judges may still fall within the scope of the original consent of states.

Unlike judges, whose appointments are regulated by the founding treaties, judicial institutions generally enjoy a wide margin of discretion in determining their procedures and work methods, which are set internally.¹⁰⁰ For example, Article 39(2) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) states that:¹⁰¹

“The Committee shall establish its own rules of procedure, but these rules shall provide, inter alia, that:

- (a) Twelve members shall constitute a quorum;
- (b) Decisions of the Committee shall be made by a majority vote of the members present.”

Accordingly, states granted their original consent to allow rules of procedure to be adopted and modified by the Committee’s decision-makers. It follows that, with respect to the more technical functions that AI can fulfill, there is no need for specific state consent, since states have already granted courts the autonomy to determine and adjust their internal processes. Therefore, there seems to be no special interest or expectation of countries that procedural AI functions, such as translation, transcripts, and even legal research and evidence handling, must be carried out solely by human beings.

This leads to the question of how far AI can be integrated into the work of courts without giving rise to a legitimate expectation of states’ prior consent. I propose that the appropriate standard should, to some extent, mirror the standard used for determining how much authority may legitimately be delegated to non-judicial professionals, such as legal clerks.¹⁰² Under this

⁹⁹ Statute of the International Court of Justice, June 26, 1945, 59 STAT. 1055, T.S. No. 993.

¹⁰⁰ See, e.g., Rules of Procedure of the Human Rights Committee, CCPR/C/3/Rev.11.

¹⁰¹ International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), art. 28(1), Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 180.

¹⁰² See, e.g., Charles H. Sheldon, *Law Clerking with a State Supreme Court: Views from the Perspective of the Personal Assistants to the Judges*, 6 JUST. SYS. J. 346 (1981) (addressing the need to trust that judges delegate tasks and retain the ultimate responsibility, and emphasizing that the judge makes the crucial decisions by voting and signing the final opinion); John Bilyeu Oakley & Robert S. Thompson, *Law Clerks in Judges’ Eyes: Tradition and Innovation in the Use of Legal Staff by American Judges*, 67 CALIF. L. REV. 1286 (1979) (noting that the extent of opinion writing delegated to law clerks varies greatly among judges, ranging from some judges never allowing a clerk to pen a word to others delegating opinion writing to the point of dependence); Chad Oldfather & Todd C. Peppers, *Judicial Assistants or Junior Judges: The Hiring, Utilization, and Influence of Law Clerks*, 98 MARQ. L. REV. 1 (2014) (discussing the fundamental question whether law clerks exercise

approach, as long as the AI tools providing judicial decision-making support operate under judicial oversight by one of the judges (a “judge” in the loop), and the final decision remains with the judge, their use may be regarded as falling within the scope of the original consent of states, and as not undermining the normative legitimacy of the institution.

Moreover, it might be argued that, in certain regards, the use of AI could even strengthen the element of state consent. As noted above, many states and even some legal scholars have long contended that courts have significantly expanded their jurisdiction through overinterpretation of treaties, in ways that depart from the original consent of states. Against this background, using AI for tasks such as legal research and drafting legal judgments may promote greater consistency in judicial reasoning and decisions and reduce the scope for interpretative discretion deemed excessive by many states.

ii. Procedural Fairness for the Litigants

Procedural fairness for litigants, both state and non-state actors, is regarded as one of the basic components of normative legitimacy of IJIs. The concept of procedural fairness is broad and may encompass a wide range of other criteria, such as bias, transparency, and legality. As these aspects are addressed in more detail in other parts of the article, this discussion adopts a *narrower* approach of procedural justice. Therefore, this section addresses only the components of access to justice, efficiency of proceedings, and clear legal reasoning. At the outset, I would suggest that, perhaps even more than in the other aspects of normative legitimacy, AI has a special potential to improve the normative legitimacy of courts in these three areas.

(a) Access to Justice

The international legal system presents special obstacles and challenges pertaining to access to justice, as cases adjudicated before IJIs tend to be very complex, involving vast amounts of evidence and multiple languages requiring translation, and multiple jurisdictions.¹⁰³

Access to international justice can become a substantial barrier when there is a major imbalance of power or financial resources between the parties.¹⁰⁴ This is particularly evident in cases before regional human rights courts in which individuals file claims against states. In such proceedings, states are usually represented by experienced lawyers and have extensive resources at their disposal to litigate the case, whereas applicants must bear the costs of their lawyers and related legal expenses in a foreign court. In the past, this imbalance was to some extent mitigated by the involvement of pro bono

inappropriate levels of influence over the judicial decision-making process, directly addressing concerns about the limits of delegation and judgment).

¹⁰³ See detailed discussion, *supra* Section I.C.

¹⁰⁴ See, e.g., Francesca Farrington & Nevena Jevremović, *Between a Rock and a Hard Place: The Impact of Replacing or Abolishing ISDS on Investment-Affected Parties*, 16 J. INT’L DISP. SETTLEMENT idaf023 (2025) (arguing that emerging evidence that investor–state dispute settlement (ISDS) has been used to frustrate investment-affected parties’ access to justice); Shikhelman *supra* note 59 (discussing the challenges of access to justice in the context of the U.N.H.R.C.); Christopher A. Whytock, *Transnational Access to Justice*, 38 BERKELEY J. INT’L L. 154 (2020) (discussing barriers of access to international justice).

lawyers and NGOs.¹⁰⁵ However, neither NGOs nor lawyers have unlimited resources, and they cannot provide assistance to all individuals in need.

In light of the foregoing, AI may help to mitigate, at least to some extent, barriers to accessing the intentional system. In general, AI has been regarded as a tool capable of reducing power imbalances between parties, including by making legal proceedings more accessible.¹⁰⁶ While AI can provide some limited legal assistance, especially in uncomplicated cases, it still cannot adequately replace lawyers, and certainly not experienced ones,¹⁰⁷ especially given the complexity of most cases in IJIs. However, the use of AI tools, especially by the lawyers themselves, may offer certain tangible benefits to litigants by lowering the cost of legal services. For example, AI can assist with tasks such as document translation and organization, evidence management, and legal research. As litigation is usually billed on an hourly basis, using AI in those functions can significantly reduce legal costs, thereby making international institutions somewhat more accessible.

(b) Efficiency of Proceedings

This criterion concerns the manner in which the internal procedures of the court operate and how this affects the fairness of the process for the parties.¹⁰⁸ The most significant issue in this regard is the length of the proceedings before the IJIs. Delays are often attributable to the high volume of cases IJIs receive each year, combined with insufficient resources to process them efficiently.¹⁰⁹ For example, it has often been claimed, especially in the context

¹⁰⁵ Rachel J. Schoner, *Individual Mobilization by Victims of Human Rights Abuse: Who Files Petitions in the United Nations?*, 69 INT'L STUD. Q. sqaf043 (2025); Lloyd Hitoshi Mayer, *NGO Standing and Influence in Regional Human Rights Courts and Commissions*, 36 BROOK. J. INT'L L. 911, 913–14, 937 (2011); Freek van der Vet, *Seeking Life, Finding Justice: Russian NGO Litigation and Chechen Disappearances Before the European Court of Human Rights*, 13 HUM. RTS. REV. 303, 304 (2012).

¹⁰⁶ See, e.g., <https://donotpay.com/> (DoNotPay is an online platform that uses automation to help consumers navigate legal and bureaucratic processes, such as disputing fines, cancelling subscriptions, filing complaints, and asserting basic legal rights); <https://www.rocketlawyer.com/> (provides online legal services including legal documents, contracts, planning tools, and access to attorneys for individuals and small businesses); <https://www.painworth.com/> (aimed at personal-injury and insurance claims, using automation to help people calculate and pursue compensation); see also *Trends in State Courts 2025* (Nat'l Ctr. for State Cts. 2025) (discussing how AI can improve access to justice) chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/<https://www.ncsc.org/sites/default/files/media/document/NCS-C-Trends-2025.pdf>.

¹⁰⁷ See, e.g., *Experts Agree: Artificial Intelligence Cannot Replace Lawyers*, LAW TIMES, Mar. 31, 2025, <https://www.lawtimesnews.com/resources/legal-technology/experts-agree-artificial-intelligence-cannot-replace-lawyers/391950?>.

¹⁰⁸ Yuval Shany, *Assessing the Effectiveness of International Courts: A Goal-Based Approach*, 106 AM. J. INT'L L. (2012) (discussing in general the different ways in which the effectiveness of international courts can be assessed); Geir Ulfstein, *The Human Rights Treaty Bodies and Legitimacy Challenges*, in LEGITIMACY AND INTERNATIONAL COURTS 16 (Harlan Grant Cohen, Nienke Grossman, Andreas Føllesdal & Geir Ulfstein eds., 2018).

¹⁰⁹ For instance, in 2024, the ECtHR had more than 60,000 pending applications from across the Council of Europe's member states (<https://www.echr.coe.int/annual-reports>); the Inter-American Commission on Human Rights receives around 3,000 new petitions per year (https://www.oas.org/en/iachr/jsForm/?File=/en/iachr/media_center/preleases/2025/092.asp); according to a report by the U.N., as of December 31, 2023 1,913 communications were pending at the U.N.H.R.C. (G.A., Status of the human rights treaty body system, September 4, 2024, A/79/336).

of the ECtHR, that the Court has become a victim of its own success.¹¹⁰ In this respect, the well-known adage that “justice delayed is justice denied” is therefore highly relevant in the international legal context. Fikfak and Helfer have widely discussed the different ways in which AI and other technologies can be used in the context of IJIs to improve the efficiency of their work.¹¹¹ Their proposals include transferring certain functions, such as admissibility screening, translation, verification of format and other requirements, and the review of required information in the complaint, to technological tools to the greatest extent possible.¹¹² AI can also assist by identifying repetitive cases, enabling decisions to be made more quickly. AI can group petitions into different priority categories, which can also help judges reach decisions more efficiently.¹¹³ By performing these functions, AI has the potential to accelerate the pace of proceedings, improve efficiency, and enhance the relevance of decisions, thereby increasing normative legitimacy.

(c) Clear Standards of Legal Reasoning

Standards of legal reasoning may be defined as the accepted principles, methods, and criteria used to ensure that legal decisions are rational, coherent, consistent with the law, and normatively justified.¹¹⁴ One potential application of AI is as a decision-making support tool. However, a central concern for standards of legal reasoning is that AI operates as a “black box.”¹¹⁵ Although AI systems are trained on previous data and generate output based on it, the precise reasoning leading AI to a particular output may remain opaque. This opacity can pose significant difficulties for litigants, who may be unable to understand the basis of a decision or to challenge it effectively on appeal. These concerns are exacerbated by the risks of AI biases discussed above, both systemic and those arising from human–computer interactions. In particular, the presence of a status quo bias may lead human decision-makers to defer to AI outputs and subsequently rationalize them, rather than independently assessing the underlying reasoning.

¹¹⁰ See, e.g., Laurence R. Helfer, *Redesigning the European Court of Human Rights: Embeddedness as a Deep Structural Principle of the European Human Rights Regime*, 19 EUR. J. INT’L L. 125 (2008).

¹¹¹ Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39, at 7–13.

¹¹² Fikfak & Helfer, *supra* note 39.

¹¹³ *Id.* at 22.

¹¹⁴ Tullio Treves, *Aspects of Legitimacy of Decisions of International Courts and Tribunals*, in LEGITIMACY IN INTERNATIONAL LAW 169 (Rüdiger Wolfrum & Volker Röben eds., 2008); see generally Barbara A. Spellman & Frederick Schauer, *Standards of Legal Reasoning*, in THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF JURISPRUDENCE AND PHILOSOPHY OF LAW (Jules L. Coleman, Kenneth Einar Himma & Scott J. Shapiro eds., 2012) (discussing the different approaches to the essence of legal reasoning); Neil MacCormick, *Legal Reasoning and Interpretation*, in ROUTLEDGE ENCYCLOPEDIA OF PHILOSOPHY 950 (defining legal reasoning as the process of devising, reflecting on, or giving reasons for legal acts and decisions or justifications for speculative opinions about the meaning of law and its relevance to action).

¹¹⁵ See discussion, *supra* Part I.

iii. Consistency with the Object and Purpose of the Normative Regimes that the International Institution Interprets and Applies

The criterion of consistency focuses on the specific subject-matter international law regime applied by a tribunal.¹¹⁶ This analysis suggests that the specific field of international law in which the IJI operates, as well as the mandate, and object and purpose of the IJI itself, may be relevant when assessing the implications of the use of AI by specific institutions.

To understand the object and purpose of the regime and of the IJI, the founding documents, especially treaties, of both the specific regime and the IJI must be examined. For instance, the object and purpose of the World Trade Organization (“WTO”) Dispute Settlement Body is to “secure a positive solution to a dispute,”¹¹⁷ and the overall objective of the WTO is to “to help its members use trade as a means to raise living standards, create jobs and improves people’s lives.”¹¹⁸ Also, the purpose of the International Center for Settlement Investment Disputes (“ICSID”) is to “facilitate the settlement of investment disputes between foreign investors and host states, and thus promote international investment leading to economic development.”¹¹⁹ On the other hand, the object and purpose of the ICC is to “end impunity and thus to contribute to the prevention of international crimes,”¹²⁰ and the object and purpose of the ECtHR is to protect the rights and freedoms set out in the ECHR,¹²¹ and specifically to ensure that there is an effective remedy for individuals against state violations.¹²²

As the examples above demonstrate, while the object and purposes of various IJIs and regimes share certain similarities, they also have significant differences. With respect to the similarities, effectiveness appears to underpin all the IJIs. Viewed from the perspective of procedural efficiency, AI can play a particularly supportive role by assisting with technical functions such as registration, translation, and transcription, therefore streamlining these institutions’ processes. Moreover, given that lack of resources poses a persistent problem in the system, the use of AI for technical functions can help direct the existing resources toward less mechanical functions where more nuance and judgment are needed.

Regarding specific institutional purposes, the analysis can be somewhat more precise. While clearly both efficiency and fairness are relevant across all contexts, the balance between them may vary somewhat from field to field. In more economically oriented institutions, such as the WTO Dispute Settlement Body and ICSID, where promoting economic development is a central purpose, there may be greater scope to introduce AI to increase the efficiency of the system. Where collective economic interests tend to

¹¹⁶ Grossman, *supra* note 9.

¹¹⁷ *Understanding on Rules and Procedures Governing the Settlement of Disputes*, art. 8.8, https://www.wto.org/english/docs_e/legal_e/dsu_e.htm, para. 8

¹¹⁹ Convention on the Settlement of Investment Disputes Between States and Nationals of Other States, opened for signature Mar. 18, 1965, 575 U.N.T.S. 159 (entered into force Oct. 14, 1966).

¹²⁰ Rome Statute of the International Criminal Court, pmbl.

¹²¹ ECHR, art. 26.

¹²² *Id.* art. 13.

predominate and individual rights are generally less directly implicated,¹²³ efficiency may be accorded greater weight, without negating the important value of fairness. In these cases, AI may be given more autonomy to streamline procedures, even if this has certain drawbacks, such as limited transparency arising from “black box” decision-making or AI’s limitations in understanding nuances.

International criminal law presents a markedly different context. The stakes are exceptionally high in this field, both because of the grave nature of the alleged atrocities and the profound consequences of stigma and punishment associated with convictions for committing international crimes. For this reason, the international community may be more reluctant to apply AI because of the high stakes of an international criminal trial for a defendant. Therefore, the balance between efficiency and fairness in the integration of AI leans more strongly to the side of fairness.

Although efficiency remains an important consideration, arguably, the need for accuracy and human involvement assumes greater weight in the criminal context. While it is not necessarily clear that human oversight is always more accurate than AI-assisted processes, human decision-makers usually are better equipped to understand legal and factual nuances. However, the persistent lack of resources means that the potential advantages of AI in international criminal proceedings cannot be overlooked. The use of AI may enhance the capacity of prosecutorial offices to manage complex cases and evidence, thereby strengthening deterrence. Moreover, more efficient proceedings can benefit both defendants and victims. Accordingly, the balance between AI and human involvement that preserves the normative legitimacy of a judicial institution can depend to a great extent on the substantive field of law, and perhaps even on the public perception of the appropriateness of assigning certain tasks to AI.

iv. Democratic Legitimacy – Considering the Interests of All Stakeholders Involved

Democratic legitimacy looks into whether decision-making processes are responsive to and representative of all those affected by them. As Grossman argues in her article about the normative legitimacy of international courts, contemporary international adjudication increasingly affects the rights and duties of non-litigants, implicates a broad range of stakeholder interests, and shapes international law prospectively rather than merely resolving disputes between states.¹²⁴ Therefore, courts should take into consideration the broader impact of their decisions and provide avenues for participation or representation of stakeholders who are not official parties to the case.¹²⁵

Related concerns also arise regarding the extent to which international courts represent all those subject to their authority, reflect diverse legal traditions and perspectives, and maintain adequate mechanisms of accountability. The following sections examine the different components of

¹²³ Although the right to property and development are obviously intertwined in these proceedings.

¹²⁴ Grossman, *supra* note 9, at 87–94

¹²⁵ *Id.*

democratic legitimacy in greater detail and consider how they relate to the use of AI in IJIs.

(a) Considering the Interests of All Stakeholders

In general, the capacity to consider the interests of all stakeholders, and more specifically, to allow each of them to present their views before a judicial body, especially in the form of an *amicus curiae* brief, depends primarily on the procedural rules of the court and not on the incorporation of AI.¹²⁶

However, where the rules of an IJI already permit the representation of diverse viewpoints, the use of AI may offer valuable technical means to facilitate their inclusion in the judicial process. As noted above, international courts are often severely under-resourced. The primary mechanism for non-litigants to present their interests before the courts is through submitting *amicus curiae* briefs. Processing a large volume of lengthy *amicus curiae* briefs can be very demanding, and may not always receive sufficient attention, particularly as the primary responsibility of the tribunal is toward the litigants themselves.¹²⁷ In this context, AI can be used to summarize and organize these briefs, thereby assisting the relevant decision-makers to consider a broader range of perspectives. Moreover, AI may assist in helping tribunal members gain a much wider perspective of the interests, viewpoints, and practices of different groups. One illustration of this potential lies in proposals to use AI to identify the norms of customary international law.¹²⁸ As Megiddo observes in her work on the subject, international courts have traditionally relied on a very limited, and perhaps even geopolitically skewed, set of case studies to establish the two elements of customary international law – state practice and *opinion juris*.¹²⁹ Using AI models may enable the tribunals to access a much larger body of relatively unbiased information relating to both elements of customary law at a relatively low cost. In this way, AI can significantly expand the range of perspectives that tribunals are able to process and consider.

¹²⁶ This focuses mainly on the ability to bring amicus briefs to different IJIs. For instance, in the ICJ, a special permission is required in order to file amicus briefs (Statute of the International Court of Justice, arts. 34 and 66). On the other hand, the ECtHR has a relatively accessible process of filing third party interventions (ECHR, art 36 and Rules of Court, r. 44). *See also*, Lance Bartholomeusz, *The Amicus Curiae Before International Courts and Tribunals*, 5 NON-ST. ACTORS & INT'L L. 209 (2005) (discussing the juridical nature of friend of the court briefs); Paul M. Collins, Jr., *The Use of Amicus Briefs*, 14 ANN. REV. L. & SOC. SCI. 219–37 (2018) (providing a critical review of scholarship on amicus curiae briefs); Hannah Woolaver & Sarah Williams, *The Role of the Amicus Curiae Before International Criminal Tribunals*, 6 INT'L CRIM. L. REV. 151–89 (2006) (discussing the role of amicus briefs in international legal proceedings).

¹²⁷ *See, e.g.*, Lucas Bastin, *The Amicus Curiae in Investor–State Arbitration*, 1 CAMBRIDGE J. INT'L & COMP. L. 208–34 (2012) (bringing concerns about amicus curiae participation, such as the increase in costs and delays, are real problems that militate against their inclusion).

¹²⁸ Tamar Megiddo, *Modelling Custom: Big Data, AI and Customary International Law (from Scarcity to Abundance: Customary International Law in the Age of AI)* (Jan. 27, 2025), SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5115997> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5115997>.

¹²⁹ *Id.* at 29–36.

(b) Representation

Even where an institution's decisions are substantively just, normative legitimacy also requires that they be rendered by decision-makers who represent those subject to the institution's jurisdiction.¹³⁰ Some scholars have pointed out that there is a democratic deficit regarding the authority of international institutions, and have argued that greater diversity within the judiciary could help to mitigate this problem.¹³¹ Hence, the diversity of the bench of the IIJs is of special importance.

One of the assumptions behind the diversity expectation is that the decision-making process might be influenced by the background of the decision-makers. A non-representative bench may potentially influence outcomes in ways that reflect particular geopolitical or cultural perspectives. However, despite extensive discussion in the literature, the reality is that a lack of diversity among decision-makers persists in many IIJs.¹³² Although efforts have been made in recent years to broaden diversity within international judicial bodies, the issue remains a significant challenge. AI is not a human judge and therefore does not possess the conventional attributes of representation associated with judicial decision-makers.

At first glance, given the persistent challenges surrounding representation in international courts, the option of using AI, at least for decision-support functions, seems to offer at least a partial response to the lack of representation. Arguably, using AI for decision-making support can render the outcomes somewhat less dependent on the specific composition of the bench at the time of the decision-making and be perceived as reducing the influence of individual biases.

However, here once again, certain biases associated with the AI itself can reemerge when it is deployed for decision-making support. As mentioned above, two main biases are relevant: those inherent in the dataset and those of human deference to the algorithm. Of these, the more troubling is the "inherent" bias. In certain respects, dataset-related bias may even exacerbate the effects of a longstanding lack of representation. This is because AI systems are trained and rely on past decisions, which were often produced by

¹³⁰ Grossman, *supra* note 9, at 67; Antoinette Scherz & Oisín Suttle, *Legitimate International Authority and Institutional Diversity*, CRITICAL REV. INT'L SOC. & POL. PHIL. 1–12 (2025); Vera Shikhelman, *Diversity and Decision-Making in International Judicial Institutions: The United Nations Human Rights Committee as a Case Study*, 36 BERKELEY J. INT'L L. 60 (2018); Neus Torbisco-Casals, *The Legitimacy of International Courts: The Challenge of Diversity*, 52 J. SOC. PHIL. 491–515 (2021).

¹³¹ Daniel Bodansky, *The Legitimacy of International Governance: A Coming Challenge for International Environmental Law?*, 93 AM. J. INT'L L. 596, 613 (1999) (discussing the importance of a democratic procedure and decision-making process to the legitimacy of international law in general, and specifically to international environmental law); Kate Malleson, *Diversity in the Judiciary: The Case for Positive Action*, 36 J.L. & SOC'Y 376, 377 (2009); Yuval Shany, *No Longer a Weak Department of Power? Reflections on the Emergence of a New International Judiciary*, 20 EUR. J. INT'L L. 73, 89–90 (2009).

¹³² OHCHR, Concept Paper on the High Commissioner's Proposal for a Unified Standing Treaty Body para. 22 (2006); Vera Shikhelman, *Diversity and Decision-Making in International Judicial Institutions: The United Nations Human Rights Committee as a Case Study*, 36 BERKELEY J. INT'L L. 60 (2018); Nicole G. Iannarone, *Structural Barriers to Inclusion in Arbitrator Pools*, 96 WASH. L. REV. 1389 (2021); Juliana Santos de Carvalho & Justina Uriburu, *Problematising Diversity: The Change that International Lawyers (Do Not) Want for International Courts*, 10 LONDON REV. INT'L L. 391–425 (2022); Milena Sterio, *Women as Judges at International Criminal Tribunals*, TRANSNAT'L L. & CONTEMP. PROBS. 219 (2019).

even less diverse benches. As a result, AI may entrench patterns shaped by earlier inequalities in representation. Moreover, reliance on AI for decision-making support risks reinforcing older and outdated points of view and may impede the development of more progressive approaches introduced by newer and more diverse judges.

(c) Accountability

Accountability is a central concern from the perspective of democratic legitimacy.¹³³ Accountability entails the ability to hold institutions and their personnel accountable for their conduct.¹³⁴ IJIs are generally subject to some degree of accountability to external bodies. For example, the ECtHR is accountable to the Council of Europe,¹³⁵ the ICC is accountable to the Assembly of States,¹³⁶ and the ICJ is accountable to the U.N. General Assembly and U.N. Security Council.¹³⁷ However, the specific question of who bears responsibility for actions performed by AI remains unresolved. This issue is particularly significant given broader concerns about AI accountability and the fact that many AI systems operate as a “black box,” making it difficult to trace the reasoning processes and considerations that the AI applied in making their outputs. However, it appears unlikely that delegating certain procedural or substantive functions to AI would absolve either the institution as a whole or the professionals using the AI tools of responsibility. Rather, accountability for errors is likely to remain with the human professionals overseeing and relying on AI systems, whether it be the Secretariat in relation to technical functions, the legal assistants with respect to legal research, or judges in the context of decision-making support. It follows that institutional accountability as a whole remains unchanged, and the introduction of AI does not result in an accountability vacuum.

v. *Effectiveness and Implementation*

This section examines three related, and even interconnected, components of normative legitimacy: independence and impartiality, compliance with IJIs’ decisions and the effectiveness of remedies, and constraints on the development of international law.

(a) Independence and Impartiality

One of the longstanding concerns about IJIs is that they are not impartial but instead function as political actors in the international arena.¹³⁸ Relatedly,

¹³³ Andreas Føllesdal, *Survey Article: The Legitimacy of International Courts*, 28 J. POL. PHIL. 476 (2020); Geir Ulfstein, *The Human Rights Treaty Bodies and Legitimacy Challenges*, in LEGITIMACY AND INTERNATIONAL COURTS (Harlan Grant Cohen, Nienke Grossman, Andreas Føllesdal & Geir Ulfstein eds., 2018); Grossman, *supra* note 9, at 87, 92–94.

¹³⁴ Ulfstein, *supra* note 133.

¹³⁵ ECHR, arts. 46, 52

¹³⁶ Statute of the International Criminal Court, arts. 87, 118, 122.

¹³⁷ Statute of the International Court of Justice, art. 24; Charter of the United Nations, art. 94.

¹³⁸ See Erik Voeten, *International Judicial Behavior*, in THE OXFORD HANDBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL ADJUDICATION 550, 555–56 (Cesare P.R. Romano et al. eds., 2014) (elaborating on the different opinions on the matter); Erik Voeten, *International Judicial Independence*, in INTERDISCIPLINARY PERSPECTIVES ON INTERNATIONAL LAW AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS, *supra* note 93, at 421, 427, 429; Laurence R. Helfer &

scholarly debate persists over whether international courts should be understood as agents of the states that appoint their judges or as trustees of the international community.¹³⁹ Empirical research does suggest that certain biases and voting patterns do exist in the IJIs.¹⁴⁰ For example, studies have found support for the hypothesis that judges tend to rule in favor of their states of nationality in the ECtHR and the ICJ.¹⁴¹ In the context of the ICJ, it has been found that judges are more likely to rule in favor of states with similar levels of wealth, culture, and political regimes as their own states of nationality.¹⁴² By contrast, research has also shown that in regions with newer democracies, such as Eastern European and Latin American states, judicial decision-makers are more likely to vote against their states of origin.¹⁴³

Concerns about impartiality and bias have been particularly prominent in recent years in relation to two major institutions: ICSID and the ICC. As discussed above, ICSID, a World Bank institution, is responsible for resolving legal disputes between foreign investors and sovereign states through arbitration and conciliation. Critics have argued that ICSID exhibits a structural bias in favor of the investors, who usually come from developed states, rather than respondent states, which are usually developing states.¹⁴⁴

Similar concerns have arisen with the ICC. While the ICC was originally established as a permanent court and as an answer to claims of selective justice of establishing *ad hoc* the International Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia and the International Criminal Tribunal for Rwanda,¹⁴⁵ it has quite quickly faced accusations of bias. The initial criticisms focus on the fact that the court, in its first years, focused on situations in African countries, and not on other situations,¹⁴⁶ a pattern that some claimed constituted a form of legal colonialism.¹⁴⁷ While various “legalistic” explanations were offered for

Anne-Marie Slaughter, *Toward a Theory of Effective Supranational Adjudication*, 107 YALE L.J. 273 (1997) (explaining why international judicial independence is important).

¹³⁹ Eric A. Posner & John C. Yoo, *Judicial Independence in International Tribunals*, 93 CALIF. L. REV. 1 (2005) (explaining that the international courts should take into account the interests of states); Laurence R. Helfer & Anne-Marie Slaughter, *Why States Create International Tribunals: A Response to Professors Posner and Yoo*, 93 CALIF. L. REV. 899 (2005); Eric A. Posner & John C. Yoo, *Reply to Helfer and Slaughter*, 93 CALIF. L. REV. 957 (2005).

¹⁴⁰ See, e.g., Posner & de Figueiredo, *supra* note 63 (discussing bias in the context of the ICJ); Voeten, *supra* note 63 (*Impartiality of International Judges*) (discussing bias in the context of the ECtHR); Shikhelman, *supra* note 63 (*Geography, Politics and Culture*) (discussing bias in the context of the U.N.H.R.C.).

¹⁴¹ See Posner & de Figueiredo, *supra* note 140; Voeten, *supra* note 63 (*Impartiality of International Judges*) (discussing bias in the context of the ECtHR).

¹⁴² Posner & de Figueiredo, *supra* note 63.

¹⁴³ Shikhelman, *supra* note 63 (*Geography, Politics and Culture*) (showing that Committee Members from Eastern European and Latin American states are more likely to vote against states from their regions); Erik Voeten, *supra* note 63 (*Impartiality of International Judges*) (showing that judges from former socialist states are more likely to be activist).

¹⁴⁴ Sergio Puig & Anton Strezhnev, *Affiliation Bias in Arbitration: An Experimental Approach*, 46 J. LEGAL STUD. 371 (2016).

¹⁴⁵ Yusuf Aksar, IMPLEMENTING INTERNATIONAL HUMANITARIAN LAW: FROM THE AD HOC TRIBUNALS TO A PERMANENT INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT (2004).

¹⁴⁶ Abhinav Chandrachud, *Diversity and the International Criminal Court: Does Geographic Background Impact Decision Making?* 38 BROOK. J. INT’L L. 487, 490–502 (2013) (discussing the lack of diversity and voting patterns in the ICC).

¹⁴⁷ Lea Ina Schneider, *The International Criminal Court (ICC)—A Postcolonial Tool for Western States to Control Africa?*, 1 J. INT’L CRIM. L. 90–109 (2020) (examining the question of whether the criticism that the ICC

this focus on African states, leading African states, such as South Africa and Gambia, were still dissatisfied, and almost withdrew from the jurisdiction of the Court,¹⁴⁸ and Burundi withdrew officially in 2017.¹⁴⁹ More recent allegations of bias have arisen in relation to the situation in the Philippines, which led to a withdrawal of the Philippines from the jurisdiction of the ICC¹⁵⁰ and Israel/Palestine, leading to U.S. sanctions on the court.¹⁵¹ Therefore, perceived biases are an acute problem in the international legal sphere that can affect the legitimacy, compliance, and even existence of those institutions.

In this context, it may be argued that introducing AI into various judicial processes of the judicial institutions, particularly in decision-making support, could lead international courts' decisions to be perceived as more objective and thus more normatively legitimate. Allegations of bias typically stem from the differential application of identical legal standards or factual assessments based on personal or political considerations, whether explicit or implicit. From this perspective, using AI for decision-making support may contribute to reducing such biases and thereby enhance the perceived legitimacy of the system.

However, this potential is again subject to the caveat that the datasets used to train AI systems may be biased, and therefore, the outputs generated by these systems may reproduce these biases. This can be the case, for example, if the tribunal's own jurisprudence favors certain categories of litigants over others. In such cases, AI might be less effective in addressing deeply embedded structural biases. Nevertheless, AI-based decision-support systems

functions as a postcolonial tool for Western countries to control African countries is justified); W. Chadwick Austin & Michael Thieme, *Is the International Criminal Court Anti-African?*, 28 PEACE REV. 342–50 (2016) (argues that the ICC is a form of “imperialism” that seeks to “undermine people from poor and African countries, and other powerless countries in terms of economic development and politics”); Torque Mude et al., INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL LAW AND THE NEO-COLONIAL CONTRACT: AFRICA’S QUAGMIRE AND PROSPECTS FOR SUSTAINABLE DECOLONISATION, 57–72 (2024) (arguing that the ICC’s selective application of international criminal law and manipulation of universal jurisdiction targeting Africans is arguably designed to perpetuate neo-colonialism by controlling Africa from a distance); Harmen van der Wilt, *Universal Jurisdiction Under Attack: An Assessment of African Misgivings Towards International Criminal Justice as Administered by Western States*, 9 J. INT’L CRIM. JUST. 1043 (2011); *African Union Accuses ICC of “Hunting” Africans*, BBC NEWS (May 27, 2013), <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-22681894>; see also Chandrachud, *supra* note 145, at 511–13; Farouk Chothia, *Africa’s Fatou Bensouda Is New ICC Chief Prosecutor*, BBC NEWS (Dec. 12, 2011), <http://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-16029121>; Somini Sengupta, *As 3 African Nations Vow to Exit, International Court Faces Its Own Trial*, N.Y. TIMES (Oct. 26, 2016), https://www.nytimes.com/2016/10/27/world/africa/africa-international-criminal-court.html?_r=0.

¹⁴⁸ <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-39204035>; <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-37771592>.

¹⁴⁹ ICC, *Situation in Burundi*, <https://www.icc-cpi.int/situations/burundi>.

¹⁵⁰ Gavin Blackburn, *ICC Removes Chief Prosecutor from Duterte Case over Perceived Conflict of Interest*, EURONEWS (Oct. 15, 2025), <https://www.euronews.com/2025/10/15/icc-removes-chief-prosecutor-from-duterte-case-over-perceived-conflict-of-interest>; <https://www.icc-cpi.int/philippines#:~:text=ICC%20jurisdiction%20in%20the%20Philippines,country%20gave%20notification%20of%20withdrawal>.

¹⁵¹ *Imposing Sanctions on the International Criminal Court*, 90 Fed. Reg. (Feb. 6, 2025), <https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2025/02/imposing-sanctions-on-the-international-criminal-court/>; see also Jeremie Bracka, *A False Messiah? The ICC in Israel/Palestine and the Limits of International Criminal Justice*, 54 VAND. J. TRANSNAT’L L. 283 (2021); Richard H. Steinberg, *Politics and Justice at the International Criminal Court*, 57 ISR. L. REV. 308–50 (2024).

may still play a meaningful role in mitigating bias and strengthening the legitimacy of IJIs.

(b) Compliance with Courts' Decisions and Effectiveness of Remedies

It is argued that normative legitimacy also requires consideration of compliance with courts' decisions and the effectiveness of remedies.¹⁵² Although the measurement of compliance with international judicial decisions, and even more so, the effectiveness of international courts, has been the subject of great debate,¹⁵³ these questions need not be examined in depth for the purposes of this article. This is because, in the context of AI use in courts, the issue is largely empirical, and there is not yet sufficient research or evidence to assess how AI affects the compliance with and the effectiveness of international court decisions. As will be elaborated in the section about social legitimacy—¹⁵⁴ there is some existing general research on perceptions of the integration of AI into legal systems, albeit not necessarily international ones, but the results are relatively mixed. At the same time, international institutions are frequently criticized for a lack of consistency in the remedies and awards they grant. In this respect, AI can help introduce greater standardization and predictability, which could, in turn, contribute to improved compliance with decisions and effectiveness of remedies.

(c) Restrictions on the Development of International Law

All legal systems evolve over time in response to changing circumstances and new moral understandings reflecting broader changes in society.¹⁵⁵ The same is true of international law and international legal institutions.¹⁵⁶ While treaties are often slow, or even very difficult, to amend, societal understandings across the world have shifted significantly over the years. This evolution is particularly evident in the field of international human rights, but is not limited to it. For example, the scope of conduct understood to fall within the definition of “torture” has evolved over time.¹⁵⁷ Moreover,

¹⁵² *supra* note 133, at 10-15.

¹⁵³ Yuval Shany, *Assessing the Effectiveness of International Courts: A Goal-Based Approach*, 106 AM. J. INT'L L. 225–70 (2012) (discussing the different ways to assess the effectiveness of international courts); S. Grewal & E. Voeten, *Are New Democracies Better Human Rights Compliers?*, 69 INT'L ORG. 497 (2015) (finding that new democracies do implement similar ECtHR judgments initially more quickly than established democracies, but this effect reverses the longer a judgment remains pending); Vera Shikhelman, *Implementing Decisions of International Human Rights Institutions—Evidence from the United Nations Human Rights Committee*, 30 EUR. J. INT'L L. 753–77 (2019) (assessing under which conditions states implement the views of the U.N.H.R.C.).

¹⁵⁴ See part II.B., *infra*.

¹⁵⁵ See, generally, Lawrence M. Friedman, *On Legal Development*, 24 RUTGERS L. REV. 11 (1969); Giuseppe Dari-Mattiacci et al., *The Dynamics of the Legal System*, J. ECON. BEHAV. & ORG. 95–107 (2011); Oona A. Hathaway, *Path Dependence in the Law: The Course and Pattern of Legal Change in a Common Law System*, 86 IOWA L. REV. 601 (2000).

¹⁵⁶ See, e.g., Ingo Venzke, HOW INTERPRETATION MAKES INTERNATIONAL LAW: ON SEMANTIC CHANGE AND NORMATIVE TWISTS (2012).

¹⁵⁷ Baolu Metin ed., *Torture and Its Definition in International Law: An Interdisciplinary Approach* (2017) (examining how international law has evolved beyond state-perpetrated torture to recognize ill-treatment in different settings and contexts, such as domestic violence and adverse penal confinement); Nigel S. Rodley, *The Definition(s) of Torture in International Law*, 55 CURRENT LEGAL PROBS. 467–93 (2002) (elaborating on how new definitions have emerged in international criminal law instruments, such as the Rome Statute of the ICC,

there has been increased sensitivity regarding the interpretation of human rights responsibilities needed to protect women,¹⁵⁸ the cultural biases in the Western-oriented human rights world,¹⁵⁹ and the need to increase corporate responsibility as their power increases.¹⁶⁰ In response to these developments, the ECtHR has adopted the doctrine of the ECHR as a living instrument, whereby the ECHR is interpreted dynamically to remain responsive to present-day conditions and societal change.¹⁶¹ However, in the context of AI, a concern, already discussed above, is that AI systems are trained on prior jurisprudence and may not adequately reflect societal changes. As a result, deploying AI risks slowing or even preventing the development of jurisprudence in ways that could undermine normative legitimacy. In particular, the incorporation of contemporary standards into existing legal frameworks is a function that should be reserved for human decision-making. Accordingly, the potential of AI to inhibit the natural development of jurisprudence warrants serious consideration, and its role in decision-making support should be appropriately limited.

vi. Adherence to Law

Finally, one of the central criteria for assessing normative legitimacy is whether the relevant institution adheres to law and justice.¹⁶² From this perspective, the relevant question is how the use of AI by IJs aligns with the *substantive* norms set in international law regarding judicial institutions. While this issue could easily merit a dedicated article of its own, the following discussion outlines several key considerations. In certain respects, these considerations apply to both national and international courts.

The most important source of the right to due process in judicial proceedings is Article 14 of the ICCPR, which guarantees due process in courts.¹⁶³ Comparable due process provisions appear in regional human rights treaties, including Article 6 of the ECHR,¹⁶⁴ Articles 7 and 26 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights,¹⁶⁵ and Articles 8 and 25 of the Inter-American Convention on Human Rights.¹⁶⁶ Here, as in other sections, it is useful to distinguish between using AI for technical functions and in more substantive ways.

Article 14(1) of the ICCPR clearly states that “everyone shall be entitled to a fair and public hearing by a competent, independent and impartial tribunal

and new case law from international penal tribunals, such as the International Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY), affecting the understanding of torture).

¹⁵⁸ Alice Edwards, *The “Feminizing” of Torture Under International Human Rights Law*, 19 LEIDEN J. INT'L L. 349–91 (2006).

¹⁵⁹ Makau Mutua, HUMAN RIGHTS: A POLITICAL AND CULTURAL CRITIQUE (2002); Guyora Binder, *Cultural Relativism and Cultural Imperialism in Human Rights Law*, 5 BUFF. HUM. RTS. L. REV. 211 (1999).

¹⁶⁰ Steven R. Ratner, *Corporations and Human Rights: A Theory of Legal Responsibility*, 111 YALE L.J. 443–546 (2001).

¹⁶¹ See George Letsas, *The Truth in Autonomous Concepts: How to Interpret the ECHR*, 15 EUR. J. INT'L L. 279–305 (2004).

¹⁶² Grossman, *Normative Legitimacy*, *supra* note 9, at 97–100.

¹⁶³ ICCPR, art. 28, Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 171.

¹⁶⁴ Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms, Nov. 4, 1950, 213 U.N.T.S. 221.

¹⁶⁵ African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights, June 27, 1981, 1520 U.N.T.S. 217.

¹⁶⁶ American Convention on Human Rights, Nov. 22, 1969, 1144 U.N.T.S. 123.

established by law.”¹⁶⁷ In General Comment 32,¹⁶⁸ the Human Rights Committee further elaborated on the interpretation of “impartial” and “independent.” Regarding “impartiality,” the Human Rights Committee states that:¹⁶⁹

“The requirement of impartiality has two aspects. First, judges must not allow their judgement to be influenced by personal bias or prejudice, nor harbour preconceptions about the particular case before them, nor act in ways that improperly promote the interests of one of the parties to the detriment of the other. Second, the tribunal must also appear to a reasonable observer to be impartial.”

Regarding “independence,” the General Comment states:¹⁷⁰

The requirement of independence refers, in particular, to the procedure and qualifications for the appointment of judges [...] and the actual independence of the judiciary from political interference by the executive branch and legislature. States should take specific measures guaranteeing the independence of the judiciary, protecting judges from any form of political influence in their decision-making.

Finally, Article 14(1) of the ICCPR also mentions the “competence” of a tribunal as a requirement of due process.¹⁷¹ Unlike the provisions on impartiality and independence, General Comment 32 does not elaborate on the definition of competence. However, it should be noted that some scholars have argued that there is a basic human right for a case to be determined by a human judge rather than by an AI system.¹⁷² One justification offered for this position is the absence of “role-reversibility” between humans subject to the law and an AI system acting as a “judge.”¹⁷³

As noted above, there are differing perspectives on whether substantive uses of AI enhance or undermine the impartiality and independence of tribunals. On the one hand, AI-assisted decision-making support may promote greater independence and impartiality by reducing the influence of external influences and individual biases and by encouraging a more consistent application of facts to existing jurisprudence. On the other hand, such use may entrench the system’s inherent biases and risk becoming a *de facto* and prohibited delegation of authority to AI. These are also some of the

¹⁶⁷ ICCPR, Dec. 16, 1966, 999 U.N.T.S. 180.

¹⁶⁸ Human Rights Comm., *Gen. Comment No. 32: Article 14: Right to Equality Before Courts and Tribunals and to a Fair Trial*, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/GC/32, para. 21 (Aug. 23, 2007) [hereinafter General Comment 32].

¹⁶⁹ *Id.* para. 21.

¹⁷⁰ *Id.* para. 19.

¹⁷¹ ICCPR, art. 28(1).

¹⁷² See, e.g., Jonathan Ames, *Call for Human Right to Have Legal Case Heard by a Person, Not AI*, THE TIMES, Dec. 24, 2024, <https://www.thetimes.com/uk/law/article/call-for-human-right-to-have-legal-case-heard-by-a-person-not-ai-lq5vb3k22>.

¹⁷³ Kiel Brennan-Marquez & Stephen E. Henderson, *Artificial Intelligence and Role-Reversible Judgment*, 109 J. CRIM. L. & CRIMINOLOGY 137–64 (2019).

concerns that led the European Union and UNESCO to limit the possibility of delegating decision-making completely to AI.¹⁷⁴

An open question obviously remains over how far decision-making support can be delegated to AI while remaining within the boundaries described in Article 14. While this article has provided some preliminary answers to this question in its discussion of the consent requirement, more specific guidelines from authoritative sources of international law are needed.

Additionally, Article 14(5) of the ICCPR states that “[e]veryone convicted of a crime shall have the right for his conviction and sentence being reviewed by a higher tribunal according to law.”¹⁷⁵ It could be argued that where a decision is made with the help of AI, the “black box” problem limits the ability to identify the reasoning behind the decision. This opacity may undermine the accused’s ability to file a proper appeal. Notably, the ICCPR does not expressly require that the parties to the trial receive a detailed judgement, in contrast to the explicit requirement in Article 14(3) to receive the nature and cause of the charge. Nevertheless, it could be contended that, particularly in cases involving AI-assisted decision-making, a requirement of sufficient reasoning should be read into the article to give meaningful effect to the right of review.

Moreover, AI has the potential to help with the problem of fragmentation that exists in international law.¹⁷⁶ As international law has expanded over recent decades, distinct bodies of rules, courts, and institutions have developed their treaty frameworks and jurisprudence, including in areas such as trade law, human rights law, environmental law, and investment law. This diversification creates challenges for the coherence, unity, and predictability of international law as a whole. A key practical consequence of fragmentation is that states may be subject to differing standards across regimes, enabling them to select the rules most favorable to their interests,¹⁷⁷ and, in some situations, to international obligations altogether.

The use of AI cannot, of course, fully solve the problem of fragmentation in international law. However, AI may, at least partially, assist IJs by enabling them to process information about how other tribunals have interpreted similar or related legal concepts and situations. This, in turn, can help judicial decision-makers better understand how their rulings interact with broader international legal norms and appreciate the wider implications better.

Thus far, the discussion has focused on the more *substantive* roles AI can play in IJs and their implications for adherence to legal standards. By contrast, with respect to the more *technical* functions that AI can perform, it can be argued that AI can significantly contribute to securing due process, particularly by promoting timely and efficient proceedings. Effective remedies and the avoidance of undue delays in trials are seen as important

¹⁷⁴ For discussion, see *supra* Section II.B.

¹⁷⁵ ICCPR.

¹⁷⁶ See, e.g., Gerhard Hafner, *Pros and Cons Ensuing from Fragmentation of International Law* 25 MICH. J. INT’L L. 849 (Summer 2004); Pierre-Marie Dupuy, *A Doctrinal Debate in the Globalisation Era: On the “Fragmentation” of International Law*, 1 EUR. J. LEGAL STUD. 25 (Summer 2007).

¹⁷⁷ See, e.g., Anne Peters, *The Refinement of International Law: From Fragmentation to Regime Interaction and Politicization*, 15 INT’L J. CONST. L. 671–704 (2017).

components of due process.¹⁷⁸ Research has shown that AI and technology in general can assist in achieving those goals.¹⁷⁹ This can be especially relevant for functions such as translation,¹⁸⁰ helping litigants to prepare their case for the court and understand it better (access to justice),¹⁸¹ and assistance with evaluating evidence and witnesses.¹⁸² There also appears to be no inherent human rights objection to the use of AI for purely technical functions, unless it can be demonstrated that such use is, on average, less accurate than a human performing these functions, and therefore risks compromising the fairness of proceedings.

vii. Conclusion – Normative Legitimacy and AI

Reaching a single overall conclusion regarding the normative legitimacy of IJIs in relation to AI is challenging because normative legitimacy comprises multiple components and criteria, and different applications of AI may influence each of them in distinct ways. To assess the broader picture, it is useful to return to Raz’s framework, which shifts the focus away from individual components of normative legitimacy toward the overarching question of whether incorporating AI into the work of judicial institutions enhances states’ and other relevant actors’ compliance with international law.

Regarding the more technical functions that the AI can perform or replace, the answer is relatively clear that AI has considerable potential to make IJIs more effective and efficient, thus increasing the likelihood that international law is applied more consistently by the relevant actors. The assessment becomes more complex when considering more substantive uses of AI. However, it can be argued that limited applications of AI, such as in decision-making support functions with human oversight, may enhance the normative legitimacy of IJIs.

B. Sociological Legitimacy

Sociological legitimacy is defined by Buchanan and Keohane as an institution that “is widely believed to have the right to rule.”¹⁸³ Unlike normative legitimacy, which is primarily a theoretical concept, sociological legitimacy raises essentially empirical questions and can be assessed through surveys, interviews, and experiments. Sociological legitimacy is particularly significant in the context of international law, where no central enforcement system exists. As a result, compliance with institutional decisions depends to a considerable extent on national and international perceptions of, and attitudes toward, those institutions.

A related question involves identifying the relevant audience to assess sociological legitimacy, that is, in whose “eyes” should the institution be regarded as legitimate? Traditionally, legitimacy in international law has been

¹⁷⁸ General Comment 32, para. 27; *see, e.g., Perterer v. Austria*, Comm. No. 1015/2001, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/81/D/1015/2001 (July 20, 2004); *Dudko v. Australia*, Comm. No. 1347/2005, U.N. Doc. CCPR/C/90/D/1347/2005 (July 23, 2007).

¹⁷⁹ See J.J. Prescott, *Improving Access to Justice in State Courts with Platform Technology*, 70 VAND. L. REV. 1993 (2017), https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3080615.

¹⁸⁰ ICCPR, art. 14(3)(f).

¹⁸¹ *Id.* art. 14(3)(b) and (d).

¹⁸² *Id.* art. 14(3)(e).

¹⁸³ Buchanan & Keohane, *supra* note 10, at 407.

assessed primarily from the perspective of the states themselves.¹⁸⁴ However, states are not living entities, raising the further question of which internal processes within the state determine that legitimacy.¹⁸⁵ These processes can involve a range of actors, including the wider public, governments, and diplomats.¹⁸⁶

Beyond states, other actors in the international arena may also be relevant for sociological legitimacy, such as NGOs, international organizations, and scholars of international relations and international law.¹⁸⁷ Notably, recent theory and research have increasingly emphasized the perceptions and opinions of the broader public, viewing them as the ultimate audience for the legitimacy of international institutions.¹⁸⁸

To the best of the author's knowledge, there is no specific empirical research examining public opinion regarding the use of AI in international courts. What does exist is some general research about the public attitudes toward the legitimacy of international institutions, as well as studies about the legitimacy of AI use in national courts. While all these strands of research can offer some guidance in assessing the sociological legitimacy of AI use by IIJs, substantially more targeted research is needed in this field.

i. Empirical Research on Public Opinion and the Legitimacy of International Institutions

Research indicates that public opinion is sensitive to the legitimacy of international institutions. For example, a recent study by Steinberg and McDowell found that in an experimental setting, the presence of Black leaders in international organizations was positively correlated with perceptions of legitimacy among Black citizens.¹⁸⁹ In another study, Ecker-Ehrhardt and his colleagues found that people perceive international organizations as having distinct ideological profiles, which in turn influences their beliefs in their legitimacy. They also found that political ideology is a significant factor in shaping attitudes toward international cooperation.¹⁹⁰

Finally, earlier research by Anjum and his colleagues found that U.N. endorsement increased support for all of the policy reforms evaluated, and that respondents who were previously informed that the U.N. had proposed the reforms were more likely to express willingness to mobilize in ways that

¹⁸⁴ Jens Steffek, *Legitimacy in International Relations: From State Compliance to Citizen Consensus*, in *LEGITIMACY IN AN AGE OF GLOBAL POLITICS* 175–92 (2007).

¹⁸⁵ Laurence R. Helfer & Karen J. Alter, *Legitimacy and Lawmaking: A Tale of Three International Courts*, 14 *THEORETICAL INQ. L.* 479 (July 2013).

¹⁸⁶ Magdalena Bexell, Kristina Jönsson & Nora Stappert, *Whose Legitimacy Beliefs Count? Targeted Audiences in Global Governance Legitimation Processes*, 24 *J. INT'L REL. & DEV.* 483–508 (2021).

¹⁸⁷ *Id.*; Jennifer Gronau & Henning Schmidtke, *The Quest for Legitimacy in World Politics—International Institutions' Legitimation Strategies*, 42 *REV. INT'L STUD.* 535–557 (2016); Tobias Lenz & Fredrik Söderbaum, *The Origins of Legitimation Strategies in International Organizations: Agents, Audiences and Environments*, 99 *INT'L AFF.* 899–920 (2023).

¹⁸⁸ Jens Steffek, *Why IR Needs Legitimacy: A Rejoinder*, 10 *EUR. J. INT'L REL.* 485–90 (2004).

¹⁸⁹ David A. Steinberg & Daniel McDowell, *Race, Representation, and the Legitimacy of International Organizations*, 78 *INT'L ORG.* 575–99 (2024).

¹⁹⁰ Matthias Ecker-Ehrhardt et al., *Ideology and Legitimacy in Global Governance*, 78 *INT'L ORG.* 731–65 (2024).

could improve the probability of their implementation.¹⁹¹ At the same time, Anjum and his colleagues also found that the U.N. endorsement had essentially no effect on respondents who did not previously have confidence in the U.N.¹⁹²

The research discussed above indicates that lay people are interested in and have opinions about international institutions and their legitimacy, and that public perceptions may be influenced by factors such as racial group membership. Specifically, in the case of racial representation, the findings further suggest that public opinion is sensitive to the source of decision-making. Accordingly, public perceptions of the use of AI in different functions of international courts may be significant. might be meaningful.

ii. Empirical Studies Regarding Perceptions of Use of AI in Dispute Resolution

This section reviews the general empirical literature on perceptions of the use of AI in dispute resolution. The number of research studies discussing this question is relatively limited. While the author is aware of only four studies directly addressing legitimacy,¹⁹³ there is also a broader body of work exploring related concepts, including fairness, trust, and acceptance.¹⁹⁴ With respect to research that focuses specifically on perceptions of legitimacy, several aspects have been explored. A study by Fine and her colleagues looked into how the public perceives judges who use AI, compared to those who rely solely on their own expertise in bail and sentencing decisions.¹⁹⁵ The study also examined how these perceptions differ across racial and ethnic groups. They found that Black participants rated judicial legitimacy higher than White and Hispanic participants, suggesting a greater openness to AI-assisted judicial decision-making in communities that have historically experienced biases in the legal system.¹⁹⁶

Another study by Fine and colleagues examined the perceptions of professional judges, in contrast to the lay participants in the previous research. This study explored whether judges believed that using AI had the potential to reduce or remove bias from bail and sentencing decisions.¹⁹⁷ The findings indicated that judges viewed AI as having the potential to inform their decision-making in these areas, while emphasizing the need for further

¹⁹¹ Gulnaz Anjum et al., *United Nations Endorsement and Support for Human Rights: An Experiment on Women's Rights in Pakistan*, 58 J. PEACE RES. 462–78 (2021).

¹⁹² *Id.*

¹⁹³ See Talia Schwartz et al., *Legitimacy of Algorithmic Decision-Making in the Age of the “Vanishing Trial”*, OHIO ST. J. ON DISP. RESOL. (forthcoming, 2026); Anna Fine et al., *Content Analysis of Judges' Sentiments Toward Artificial Intelligence Risk Assessment Tools*, 24 CRIMINOLOGY, CRIMINAL JUSTICE, LAW & SOC'Y 31 (2023); Anna Fine et al., *PUBLIC PERCEPTIONS OF JUDGES' USE OF AI TOOLS IN COURTROOM DECISION-MAKING: AN EXAMINATION OF LEGITIMACY, FAIRNESS, TRUST, AND PROCEDURAL JUSTICE* (2025); Ayelet Sela, *Can Computers Be Fair? How Automated and Human-Powered Online Dispute Resolution Affect Procedural Justice in Mediation and Arbitration*, 33 OHIO ST. J. ON DISP. RESOL. 91 (2018); Ari Ezra Waldman & Kirsten Martin, *Governing Algorithmic Decisions: The Role of Decision Importance and Governance on Perceived Legitimacy of Algorithmic Decisions*, 9 BIG DATA & SOC'Y (2022).

¹⁹⁴ Schwartz, *supra* note 193.

¹⁹⁵ Fine 2025, *supra* note 193.

¹⁹⁶ *Id.*

¹⁹⁷ Fine 2023, *supra* note 193.

research and clearer guidelines.¹⁹⁸ At the same time, the study identified a general algorithmic aversion among judges, as well as significant concerns that the use of AI could intensify bias. The judges were also concerned about how the use of AI would affect the legitimacy of the judicial system.¹⁹⁹

Moreover, a study by Sela conducted in the context of alternative dispute resolution examined how different modes of automation (human versus software) and procedural types (arbitration versus mediation) affect perceptions of legitimacy and fairness in dispute resolution systems. Although legitimacy was not explicitly operationalized in the research, it was found that participants were more open to using software in mediation than in arbitration.²⁰⁰

Finally, Waldman and Martin examined, among other issues, how perceptions of the legitimacy of algorithmic decision-making depend on the subject matter of the decision.²⁰¹ Their findings suggest that incorporating human oversight into algorithmic systems, such as maintaining human oversight, enhances perceptions of their legitimacy, even when such systems are prone to significant errors. Interestingly, they also found that perceptions of legitimacy decline more sharply when humans make errors than when algorithms make comparable errors. The positive effect of human governance on perceived legitimacy was strongest in high-stakes contexts such as parole, policing, and healthcare.²⁰²

Two studies looked into the question of the connection between the stages of the process in which AI is used and how its use is perceived. A study by Barysè and Sarel examined how AI use in different stages of the legal process affects the perceived fairness of judicial outcomes.²⁰³ The results indicated greater support for the use of AI in the more technical aspects of the process, and found no significant differences between professionals and non-professionals in this regard.²⁰⁴ In another study by Martinho, judges were surveyed about their perceptions of the fairness of using AI at different stages of the trial. This research similarly found that professional judges perceived the use of AI in the earlier stages of the process as fairer.²⁰⁵

Finally, a number of other studies may be relevant for analyzing sociological legitimacy. Locci and Massoni found that while lay people tended to prefer algorithmic judicial decision-making, legal professionals preferred human decision-making.²⁰⁶ Fine and Marsh,²⁰⁷ as well as Dhungel and Heine,²⁰⁸ showed that trust in AI varied according to the subject matter

¹⁹⁸ *Id.*

¹⁹⁹ *Id.*

²⁰⁰ Sela, *supra* note 192.

²⁰¹ Waldman & Martin, *supra* note 193.

²⁰² *Id.*

²⁰³ Dovelè Barysè & Ravid Sarel, *Algorithms in the Court: Does It Matter Which Part of the Judicial Decision-Making Is Automated?*, 32 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE & L. 117–46 (2024).

²⁰⁴ *Id.*

²⁰⁵ António Martinho, *Surveying Judges About Artificial Intelligence: Profession, Judicial Adjudication, and Legal Principles*, AI & SOC'Y (2024).

²⁰⁶ Irene Locci & Sebastien Massoni, *Judged by Robots: Preferences and Perceived Fairness of Algorithmic versus Human Punishments*, REV. L. & ECON. (2024).

²⁰⁷ Fine, Berthelot & Marsh, *supra* note 195.

²⁰⁸ Dhungel & Heine, *supra* note 36.

of the case. Haim and Yogev likewise demonstrated that acceptance of AI in decision-making varies by subject matter, with parole decisions viewed as substantially less acceptable for automation than more administrative functions, such as permit decisions.²⁰⁹

Findings concerning demographic variables and acceptance of AI in dispute resolution are inconclusive. The effects of age were inconsistent – some studies found no relationship,²¹⁰ while others indicated that younger participants were more accepting of AI.²¹¹ Results regarding gender were also inconclusive: while several studies observed greater aversion to AI use in dispute resolution settings among women,²¹² others found no significant difference.²¹³

iii. Possible Applications to Sociological Legitimacy of IJIs

The general literature surveyed above offers several insights into how AI might affect the sociological legitimacy of IJIs. First, the research suggests that there is a general openness to the introduction of AI, especially when it has a supportive function, and there is human supervision. Moreover, there seems to be much more support for the introduction of AI into the more technical functions than in actual decision-making roles. In this regard, there is no reason to believe that the view regarding IJIs would be different. The use of AI in the more technical functions may help the chronically under-resourced international system to function better, and has the potential to significantly increase its legitimacy.

By contrast, with respect to decision-making and decision-support functions, the research suggests that delegating too much power to AI, especially without human supervision, might undermine the sociological legitimacy of the court. At the same time, the use of AI may be perceived by some as potentially mitigating the biases of the system, thereby increasing the legitimacy of the institutions.

Another insight emerging from the research above is that the *subject matter* or *domain* of the decision can significantly affect perceptions of legitimacy. This consideration can extend to the type of decision, whether it is an interim decision, where it would be easier to accept wider use of AI, or a final judgment. Moreover, even within the same substantive field, different categories of cases may elicit differing views on the legitimacy of AI integration.

Repetitive cases provide a useful illustration of situations in which AI assistance may be perceived as more acceptable. A prominent example is the large number of cases brought against Italy in the ECtHR regarding the excessive delays in judicial proceedings in Italy. As mentioned above, the ECtHR found a systemic structural problem in the Italian judicial system under Article 6(1) of the ECHR, which guarantees the right to a fair trial

²⁰⁹ Amit Haim & Doron Yogev, *What Do People Want from Algorithms? Public Perceptions of Algorithms in Government*, 49 LAW & HUM. BEHAV. 263–80 (2025), <https://doi.org/10.1037/lhb0000614>.

within a “reasonable time.”²¹⁴ In these cases, the scope for judicial decision-making was very limited, as the systematic problem in the Italian legal system was well established in the Court’s jurisprudence. Therefore, more substantive decision-making support may be more acceptable from the public opinion point of view.

By contrast, cases that raise novel or highly complex issues, such as those involving human rights and climate change, as well as extraterritorial jurisdiction, are likely to warrant far less reliance on AI in decision-making and a greater degree of human discretion. Moreover, as also discussed in the section on normative legitimacy, sociological legitimacy may vary across different types of courts. There may be greater public acceptance of AI use in tribunals addressing primarily economic matters, such as commercial and investor–state arbitration, where efficiency is often a central concern. Conversely, in tribunals tasked with determining international criminal responsibility for the most serious international crimes, there might be much less sociological legitimacy for the use of AI in the more substantive dimensions.

Finally, as noted at the beginning of the chapter, assessments of legitimacy may vary depending on the particular public under consideration. The incorporation of AI may therefore have differing implications for legitimacy across groups defined by traits such as demographic background or professional status, including distinctions between legal professionals and the general public. In the context of democracy, although sociological legitimacy of IIJs is often discussed in holistic terms, the research surveyed above indicates that meaningful differences may exist across different sociological and geographical groups and should not be overlooked. Such variation may depend, among other factors, on these groups’ historical experiences with international law and international institutions. For example, international law has long been criticized as being gender-biased, and the persistence of a glass ceiling for women in the international legal world has been widely noted.²¹⁵ Moreover, as mentioned above, there is also some geopolitical opposition to international law. For example, African states have at times seen international law and international institutions as representing a new form of colonialism.

We can draw two principal conclusions from the discussion of gender and geopolitical groups above. First, it is insufficient to assess the sociological legitimacy of introducing AI into international institutions solely from a “holistic” perspective; attention must also be paid to differences among distinct social and demographic groups. Second, in the absence of targeted empirical research on the subject, it is difficult to predict the direction of support for or resistance to the use of AI within any particular group. On the one hand, some demographic groups may view the introduction of AI with greater skepticism, particularly if they believe AI systems will entrench the biases of the system against them. On the other hand, those same groups might

²¹⁴ See discussion, *supra* Part III.

²¹⁵ Nienke Grossman, *Sex on the Bench: Do Women Judges Matter to the Legitimacy of International Courts?*, 12 CHI. J. INT’L L. 647 (2011).

support more automation because they distrust human decision-makers even more and would prefer to have more clarity and objectivity introduced via AI.

A further question concerns how legal professionals, especially those working in international law, perceive the legitimacy of introducing AI, and how their views compare to those of the general public. The staff of international institutions themselves may also constitute a relevant audience for assessing sociological legitimacy. The research discussed above suggests that legal professionals tend to be more cautious about the introduction of AI into the international legal system. Concerns about professional identity and the potential impact of AI on traditional legal roles may partly explain this hesitation.

At the same time, international legal professionals may be more acutely aware than others of how problematic the lack of resources in the system is. As a result, they might be more receptive than non-international professionals to the introduction of AI features. However, the broader international public will respond to the use of AI in IJIs remains an open question. Nevertheless, given recent technological developments and the already expanding use of AI in other contexts, some degree of public support might be expected.

IV. CONCLUSION

The introduction of AI into IJIs is no longer in question. Rather, the central issue concerns the appropriate ways in which AI systems should be integrated into those institutions. As discussed above, if AI is integrated into the system thoughtfully and with due attention to potential risks, such as the reproduction of systemic vices, it may strengthen the normative legitimacy of the IJIs. In assessing the legitimacy implications of deploying AI in IJIs, it is necessary to consider factors such as substantive law, how the institution operates, and the institution's goals and even history. With respect to sociological legitimacy, there is currently no dedicated empirical research examining public opinion regarding the legitimacy of incorporating AI into IJIs. Some insights can be drawn from existing research about public opinion and the legitimacy of international institutions, as well as research about the legitimacy of incorporating AI into national legal systems. However, given the distinctive features of the international system, these findings may not be fully transferable. Therefore, targeted empirical research is needed to assess the sociological legitimacy of incorporating AI into IJIs.